

The Role of Environment on Galaxy Evolution in the Early Universe

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The Role of Environment on Galaxy Evolution in the Early Universe

Anishya Thevalil Harshan

A thesis in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
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School of Physics

Faculty of Science

The University of New South Wales

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Abstract

As one of the most extreme environments in the universe, galaxy clusters prove to be important probes of cosmology and galaxy evolution. In the local universe, galaxy populations in clusters are known to differ from the isolated/ field galaxy population in their average morphology, star formation rates, metallicities, spin, stellar mass function etc. Although the effect of environment in the local universe is well explored, how and when the evolution of cluster galaxy populations begin to diverge is not well understood. In this thesis, we explore the role of environment in the evolution of inter-stellar medium properties and star formation in the epoch when galaxy clusters are in their nascent stages. We study two protoclusters at $z \sim 2$ from the ZFIRE spectroscopic and ZFOURGE photometric surveys and use IllustrisTNG cosmological simulations to understand the onset of the effect of environment on galaxy evolution in cosmic noon.

First, we probe the interstellar medium of galaxies in a $z = 1.62$ proto-cluster with higher star formation density, considerable molecular gas fraction and tentatively low ionisation parameter (compared to the field galaxies). We measure the global electron density using the [OII] ($\lambda 3726, \lambda 3729$) doublet ratio in spectroscopic data from the Keck observatory. Contrary to the measurements at lower redshift, we find a tentative enhancement of the median electron density by a factor of three in galaxies in the UDS proto-cluster environment compared to the field galaxies at comparable redshifts, stellar mass and star formation rates. This indicates an effect of environment on the star formation history and the gas content of the galaxies. We also find that the electron density increases with redshift in both cluster and field environments from $z = 0$ to $z \sim 2$ by a factor of 10.

Next, we measure the star formation histories of galaxies in a proto-cluster at $z = 2$ using the Spectral Energy Distribution fitting module Prospector. Comparable to previous studies, we show that massive galaxies have a consistent/declining star formation history compared to the low mass galaxies that have rising star formation histories. We also find that the most massive protocluster galaxies ($\log M_*/M_\odot > 10.5$) from the ZFIRE sample are starting to show signs of star formation suppression as early as $z = 2$. The massive protocluster galaxies form $45 \pm 8\%$ of their total stellar mass in the first 2 Gyr of the universe compared to $31 \pm 2\%$ formed in the field galaxies. We compare our observational results with IllustrisTNG cosmological simulations and find similar star formation histories. Using IllustrisTNG, we further probe the physical mechanisms driving the star formation history and find that the progenitors of cluster galaxies consistently have lower gas fraction in their stellar disk compared to the progenitors of the field galaxies since

$z \sim 5$, leading to the suppression of star formation observed at $z \sim 2$.

Finally, to understand the cause of lower gas fractions in the cluster galaxies, we explore the role of environment in the accretion of gas in the early universe. We track the history of total gas accretion in satellite and central galaxies in cluster and field halos and find that the central galaxies continue to accrete gas, however the satellite galaxies in large halos ($\log M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\odot} > 13$) stop accreting gas effectively after the infall into their host halo by $z = 2$. We find that the gas inflow rates of centrals are positively correlated with the halo mass of their host halo across $z = 6$ to 2. Whereas, after the final infall, the gas inflow rates for satellite galaxies in large halos are negatively correlated with the halocentric distance and the local overdensity. These results indicate that well before the effect of environment due to gravitational and hydrodynamical processes acting on cluster galaxies becomes significant, the position of galaxies in the cosmic web in the early universe started to affect their evolution, setting stage for the eventual divergence of evolution of cluster galaxies as observed in the local universe.

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Publications and Presentations

List of Publications

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2. **Harshan, A.**, Gupta, A., Tran, K.-V. H., Alcorn, L. Y., Yuan, T., Kacprzak, G. G., Nanayakkara, T., Glazebrook, K., Kewley, L., Labb'e, I., Papovich, C. The Astrophysical Journal, 892, 77, 2020 *ZFIRE: Measuring electron density with [OII] as a function of environment at $z = 1.62$.*
3. Tran, K.-V. H., **Harshan, A.**, Glazebrook, K., Vasan G.C., K., Jones, T., Jacobs, C., Barone, T.M., Collett, T., Gupta, A., Henderson, A., Kacprzak, G. G., Kewley, L., Lopez, S., Nanayakkara, T., Sanders, R., Sweet, S. (Submitted,2021) *The AGEL Survey: Spectroscopic Confirmation of Strong Gravitational Lenses in the DES and DECaLS Fields Selected Using Convolutional Neural Networks*
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5. Gupta, A., Tran, K.-V. H., Pillepich, A., Yuan, T., **Harshan, A.** Rodriguez-Gomez, V., Genel, S., The Astrophysical Journal, 907, 95, 2021 *MOSEL and IllustrisTNG: Massive Extended Galaxies at $z = 2$ Quench Later Than Normal-size Galaxies.*
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7. Alcorn, L. Y., Gupta, A., Tran, K.-V. H., Cohn, J., Forrest, B., Glazebrook, K., **Harshan, A.**, Kacprzak, G. G., Kewley, L., Labb'e, I., Nanayakkara, T., Papovich, C., Spitler, L. R., Straatman, C. M., The Astrophysical Journal, 883, 2, 2019 *A Tale of Two Clusters: An analysis of gas-phase metallicity and nebular gas conditions in proto-clusters galaxies at $z \sim 2$.*

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Oral presentations:

1. The beginning of the end for massive galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and why environment matters, ASTRO 3D Annual Science Meeting, September 2021
2. The beginning of the end for massive galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and why environment matters, Astronomical Society of Australia Annual meeting, July 2021
3. The beginning of the end for massive galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and why environment matters, UK - National Astronomy Meeting, July 2021
4. The beginning of the end for massive galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and why environment matters, The Physics Launchpad - PhD Talks, UNSW, June 2021
5. The beginning of the end for massive galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and why environment matters, Astro 3D ECR Astronomers in Australia Seminar Series, Online, March 2021
YT Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f0VubNz9oek>
6. The beginning of the end for massive galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and why environment matters, UNSW Seminar Series, Sydney, March 2021
7. Star Formation Histories with PROSPECTOR in Proto-cluster at $z \sim 2$, The build-up of galaxies through multiple tracers and facilities, ESO - Australia Conference, Perth, Australia, February 2020
8. Environmental Effects on Electron density at $z \sim 1.6$, ASTRO3D science meeting, Sydney, Australia, May 2019
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5. Environmental Effects on Electron density at $z \sim 1.6$, UNSW Science Postgraduate Research Showcase, May 2019
6. Environmental Effects on Electron density at $z \sim 1.6$, Life and death of star-forming galaxies, Perth, Australia, March 2019

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The distribution of mass in space though homogeneous at large scales was observed to be in-homogeneous at $< 10^\circ$ angular scale by Edwin Hubble in 1934 (Hubble, 1934). The clumpy-ness of the distribution of mass at small angular scales or the tendency for "nebulae" (which we now know as Galaxies) to cluster has been known since the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries (Zwicky, 1937, 1942). As large catalogues of galaxies and their redshifts became available, the concept of the large scale structure of the universe which consists of galaxies, filaments, galaxy groups, clusters and super clusters emerged (Biviano, 2000).

In the current cosmological paradigm, the Λ Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) model (Alves et al., 2016; Hinshaw et al., 2013), large scale structure is formed by hierarchical growth. Driven by gravity, matter collapsed to form the first stars and galaxies in the over-densities observed in the primordial universe. With time, galaxies and smaller systems of galaxies or galaxy groups merged with others to form the galaxy clusters and super clusters that exist today. As the large scale structure of the universe emerged through cosmic time and galaxy clusters grew from accreting dark matter, gas, stars, galaxies, and galaxy groups, the galaxies that came to be part of these massive structures started to evolve differently. This thesis aims to understand how and when the evolution of galaxies diverged as they became part of galaxy clusters.

Figure 1.1: The Cosmic Web: Large scale structure in distribution of galaxies from the 2dFGRS map. Credit: Colless et al. (2003)

1.1 Galaxies in Galaxy Clusters

As large surveys like the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; York 2000), Two-degree Field Galaxy Redshift Survey (2dFGRS; Colless et al. 2001), Two-Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS; Crook et al. 2008) etc. became available, multi-dimensional study of galaxy properties in different environments in the local universe became possible. The effect of environment on the evolution of galaxies is observed as differences in properties in the population of galaxies in clusters/group and isolated/field galaxies. This effect is best known in the local universe with the well known morphology-density relation (Gómez et al., 2003; Houghton, 2015; Oemler, 1974). In the local universe ($z < 0.1$), the frequency of spiral and irregular galaxies decreases and the frequency of elliptical and lenticular galaxies increases with local number density of galaxies (Figure 1.2). In addition to that cluster centers also host galaxies with low star formation rates compared to field galaxies (Bluck et al., 2020; Davies et al., 2019) (e.g., Figure 1.3) and only match the value of star formation in field at distances greater than three times the virial radius (R_v) of the cluster (Lewis et al., 2002a).

Different physical processes that galaxies encounter as they fall in to the gravitational potential of a cluster leave an imprint on their properties. The effect of such environmental processes are observed in various aspects of galaxy properties beyond the morphology.

Many studies in the past show that in the local universe, galaxies in cluster environment have higher metallicities (Cooper et al., 2008; Ellison et al., 2009), higher fraction of redder galaxies (Blanton, 2006), lower star formation rates (Jarrett et al., 2017; Lewis et al., 2002a) and higher fraction of slow rotators (Cappellari et al., 2011; Cole et al., 2020) etc.

Figure 1.2: Morphology-density relation: Frequency of spirals and irregulars (S+I), lenticulars (S0) and ellipticals (E) as function of projected densities to the third nearest neighbour. Credit: Houghton (2015)

The complexity of the evolution of galaxies in different environments is presented in the weak environmental dependence of galaxy properties that are also correlated to the stellar mass of the galaxy. Disentangling the effect of environment from the effect of stellar mass of the galaxy has led to the "nature vs nurture" debate. However, the stellar mass function of galaxies in different density environments itself varies. Figure 1.4 shows the variation of stellar mass function with morphology and environment. Rich groups and cluster environments host a higher fraction of massive galaxies. The low mass galaxies $\log M_*/M_\odot < 9.5$ are predominantly late-type (blue star forming) and more frequent in poor groups and field environments. Red early type galaxies are predominantly massive and their prevalence increases with increasing number density, in contrast the blue population declines as density increases. Thus, the main role of environment might be to set

the fraction of red early-type and blue star-forming galaxies.

Figure 1.3: Mean star formation rate per unit luminosity (μ^*) decreases as galaxies approach the cluster center. Galaxies reach the value of μ^* in field (solid horizontal line) only at radial distance $R > 3R_v$. Credit: Lewis et al. (2002a)

1.2 Evolution of SFR and Galaxy Quenching

One of the key unanswered question of extra-galactic astronomy remains the role of different processes through which the star formation in a galaxy is regulated and quenched. It is broadly understood that the cold gas, which fuels star formation in a galaxy, is consumed via star formation, heated up or is removed from the galaxy (Boselli et al., 2001; Cortese et al., 2021). The removal or depletion of cold gas in the galaxy would lead to an eventual suppression of star formation, i.e., galaxy quenching.

Galaxy quenching can be driven by various different mechanisms. Galaxies can have either self - regulated growth and subsequent depletion of star formation fuel through star formation (Peng et al., 2010) and/or internal feedback mechanisms such as stellar and active galactic nuclei feedback (Croton et al., 2007; Donnari et al., 2021; Piotrowska et al., 2021; Weinberger et al., 2017; Zinger et al., 2020). Such a quenching pathway is termed as secular quenching. Another pathway, termed as environmental quenching, refers to different mechanisms experienced by galaxies in high density environments like galaxy clusters and groups.

Figure 1.4: Stellar mass function of galaxies of different morphological types as a function of environment (local galaxy density). Grey smooth curve represents the double Schechter function fit to all galaxies from Baldry et al. (2008). Credit: Blanton & Moustakas (2009)

Galaxies in high density environments have a higher probability of interacting with other galaxies in their vicinity. Interactions like galaxy mergers and tidal interactions can funnel gas into the inner regions of the galaxy or strip the galaxy of its outer low gravitationally bound gas (Boselli & Gavazzi, 2006; Moore et al., 1996; Morokuma-Matsui et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2010). Galaxies in clusters also interact with the Intra-cluster medium, which acts as a viscous force and strips the galaxy off of its star formation fuel (Ram pressure stripping; Boselli et al. 2014; Gunn & Gott $_{II}$ 1972; Lee et al. 2020; Vulcani et al. 2018).

These mechanisms deplete the cold gas content of a galaxy which accelerates the star formation suppression of galaxies in high density environments. All these mechanisms act simultaneously on galaxies in high density environments and set many fundamental observables such as the stellar mass function, quenched fraction, metallicities, ionisation conditions in the interstellar medium (ISM) etc.

1.3 Role of Environment at $z = 2$

The effect of environment is well studied in the local universe as described in the preceding sections. However, when these processes are starting to affect the evolution of galaxies is not well understood, mainly due to the lack of large scale surveys like SDSS and 2dFGRS at higher redshifts. This is further complicated by the expansion of the universe that causes the light to redshift, demanding instruments of different capabilities spanning the infrared wavelengths. Since the past decade, this gap is starting to be filled, leading to the study of high redshift universe, which is vastly different from the present day universe.

‘Cosmic noon’ ($1 < z < 3$) is described as the epoch when the cosmic star formation rate density of the universe peaked (Madau & Dickinson, 2014). This epoch describes a seminal epoch in the history of the universe, which witnessed the downturn of the star formation density in galaxies. This is also the epoch when the present day clusters are in their nascent stages and are referred to as protoclusters. Protoclusters are thus defined as several small halos clustered together without a clear central halo. These smaller clusters would eventually merge to form a central halo of virialised structure called the galaxy cluster.

The evolution of galaxies in protoclusters is thought of as diverging from their field counterparts very early in the universe. By studying the properties of stellar properties, Thomas et al. (2005) show that the early-type galaxies observed in the high density environment in the local universe have formed approximately 2 Gyrs earlier than their field counterparts. Figure 1.5 shows that the star formation in low density environment is delayed by ~ 2 Gyrs compared to galaxies in the high density environment. This suggests that the environment of a galaxy affected its star formation as early as $z > 2$.

Like in the local universe, massive clusters at $z > 1$ also host a high fraction of older (Steidel et al., 2004), red or passive galaxies (Kawinwanichakij et al., 2017a; Muzzin et al.,

Figure 1.5: Star formation histories of early type galaxies as a function of their stellar mass at the time of observation (labelled). The galaxies in higher density environment formed the majority of their stellar mass ~ 2 Gyrs earlier than their field counterparts. Credit: Thomas et al. (2005)

2012; Popesso et al., 2012), galaxies with higher metallicities (Chartab et al., 2021; Kulas et al., 2013), however, the mechanisms driving the star formation quenching and metal enrichment may be different across stellar mass and halo mass of the host (Donnari et al., 2020; Fossati et al., 2017; Sommariva et al., 2014). High redshift protoclusters also hosts a larger fraction of merger pairs (Hine et al., 2016; Watson et al., 2019) and higher AGN activity (Digby-North et al., 2010; Krishnan et al., 2017; Lehmer et al., 2013) compared to the field environment and the local universe pointing to a different pathway for star formation progression in the high redshift universe.

Despite the advances made in the observations of high redshift protocluster, a consensus on the effect of environment in determining galaxy properties is yet to be reached as contesting studies find weak to no effect of environment at $z > 1$. For example, while simulations suggest that the effect of environment on the mass-metallicity relation becomes significant at $z \sim 1.5$ (Gupta et al., 2018), studies like Alcorn et al. (2019); Kacprzak et al. (2015); Namiki et al. (2019) find no effect of environment on the mass metallicity

relation at similar redshifts. This thesis aims to further the understanding of the role of environment at and the environmental mechanisms that affect the ISM properties and star formation activity at $z \sim 2$. For this, we use ZFOURGE photometric survey (Straatman et al., 2016), ZFIRE spectroscopic survey (Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015) along with IllustrisTNG cosmological simulations (Nelson et al., 2018; Pillepich et al., 2018a).

1.3.1 ZFIRE survey

The ZFIRE (Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015) survey is a MOSFIRE/Keck (McLean et al., 2012) and LRIS/Keck (Oke et al., 1995) spectroscopic survey of rich environments at $z \sim 2$. ZFIRE spans 2 proto-cluster environments discovered using the ZFOURGE survey (Straatman et al., 2016) in the COSMOS ($z = 2.09$; Spitler et al. 2012) and the UDS ($z = 1.62$; Papovich et al. 2010) fields. These fields are well surveyed by different instruments and telescopes in surveys such as 3DHST (Hubble Space Telescope) (Momcheva et al., 2016), CANDELS (HST) (Grogin et al., 2011), COSMOS (Subaru, KPNO, CTIO and CFHT) (Capak et al., 2007) and UKIDSS (UKIRT) (Lawrence et al., 2007) providing a large set of multi-wavelength ancillary data.

The selection of galaxies from the ZFOURGE survey, which is stellar mass complete to $\log(M_*) \sim 9M_\odot$ at $z = 2$ (Tomczak et al., 2014), ensures that with ZFIRE we are able to extend the studies to a large stellar mass range (not stellar mass complete). The COSMOS field sample is selected from ZFOURGE with K AB magnitude > 24 for star forming galaxies and any detected K band observations for non star forming galaxies. The UDS field samples are selected on the basis of galaxies identified in the protocluster by Papovich et al. (2010). Ultimately, using nebular emission lines, 170 spectroscopic redshifts were identified in the COSMOS sample and 62 in the UDS field (Nanayakkara et al., 2016)(Figure 1.6). The observational constraint of K AB magnitude < 24 introduces a bias in the sample towards star forming galaxies and may miss the galaxies that are below the star formation main sequence especially at the lower mass end.

The COSMOS protocluster is identified to be $\sim 10\sigma$ overdense compared to the matter density at $z = 2.09$ Spitler et al. (2012). It has a measured velocity dispersion of $\sigma_{1D} = 552 \pm 52 \text{ km/s}$ corresponding to a virial mass of $M_{halo} = 10^{13.5 \pm 0.2} M_\odot$ (estimated by

Figure 1.6: Protoclusters discovered in the ZFOURGE survey in the COSMOS field (left) by Spitler et al. (2012) and spectroscopically confirmed by Yuan et al. (2014) to be at $z = 2.09$; and the UDS field (right) discovered by Papovich et al. (2010) and spectroscopically confirmed by Tran et al. (2015) to be at $z = 1.62$. Credit: Left Nanayakkara et al. (2016), Right Papovich et al. (2010)

comparison with Giggie-Z main simulation) and would evolve to become a virialised Virgo like cluster by $z = 0$ (Yuan et al., 2014). In the COSMOS protocluster, the gas phase metallicity (Alcorn et al., 2019; Kacprzak et al., 2015, 2016), electron density and ISM conditions (Kewley et al., 2016) and kinematics (Alcorn et al., 2016) and SFR (Tran et al., 2017) of the galaxies are similar to their field counterparts. Despite the non detection of environmental effects on the ISM properties from Kewley et al. (2016), Alcorn et al. (2019) find a tentative effect of environment on the stacked $[\text{OIII}]/\text{H}\beta$ line ratio.

Alcorn et al. (2019) find a 0.11 dex higher $[\text{OIII}]/\text{H}\beta$ ratio in the high mass $\log M_*/M_{\odot} > 9.6$ sample compared to field sample (Figure 1.7). The $[\text{OIII}]/\text{H}\beta$ is indicative of the ionization parameter and ionizing field and thus on electron density (Kewley et al., 2013, 2015). Although the low significance and low number statistic of the result makes it a tentative result, if proven with a larger and deeper data set, would indicate a difference in the ionisation condition in the cluster environment.

The UDS protocluster at $z = 1.62$ is an $> 20\sigma$ overdense region (Papovich et al., 2010) with a velocity dispersion of $\sigma_{1D} = 254 \pm 50 \text{ km/s}$ and a virial mass of $M_{\text{halo}} = 7.7 \pm 3.8 \times 10^{13} M_{\odot}$ (estimated from the X-ray detection in XMM-Newton at 2.3σ level detection; Pierre et al. 2012). There is no significant effect of environment in the mass metallicity relation and

Figure 1.7: Baldwin–Phillips–Terlevich (BPT) Diagram (Baldwin et al., 1981) of galaxies within two proto-clusters in COSMOS (left) and UDS(right) fields. Alcorn et al. (2019) find a tentative 1.1 dex higher $[\text{OIII}]/\text{H}\beta$ ratio in the stacked high mass cluster galaxy sample (large blue circle) compared to the corresponding stacked field sample (large blue star). However, in the UDS proto-cluster (right), the stacked high mass cluster galaxy sample (large green circle) have lower $[\text{OIII}]/\text{H}\beta$ ratio ($\sim 1 - 2\sigma$ confidence) compared to the corresponding stacked field sample (large green star). Credit: Alcorn et al. (2019)

dust attenuation in the protocluster galaxies, however, there is an enhanced star formation in the core of the protocluster (Tran et al., 2015). The UDS protocluster also have lower $[\text{OIII}]/\text{H}\beta$ ratio in the high mass sample compared to the field sample (Alcorn et al., 2019). The difference in results from the COSMOS and UDS protoclusters indicates a high variation between systems proving a need for further studies of these systems to understand the systematic variations and isolate the effect of environment on the evolution of galaxies.

With lower $[\text{OIII}]/\text{H}\beta$ ratio, similar star formation efficiency and a considerable molecular gas reservoir (Noble et al., 2017; Rudnick et al., 2017) at the same compactness of the proto-cluster galaxies compared to the field galaxies, the UDS proto-cluster makes an interesting object to study the ISM properties and role of environment in the evolution of the ISM properties. We study the average electron density of the UDS protocluster and report our findings in Chapter 2 of this thesis.

1.3.2 ZFOURGE survey

The FourStar galaxy evolution survey (ZFOURGE) (Straatman et al., 2016) is a legacy program with the FourStar near-infrared camera (Persson et al., 2013) on the Magellan Baade Telescope spanning the Chandra Deep Field South (CDFS; Giacomini et al. 2002), Cosmic Evolution Survey Field (COSMOS; Scoville et al. 2007) and the UKIDSS Ultra Deep Survey field (UDS; Lawrence et al. 2007). Along with deep five NIR medium band (j_1, j_2, j_3, H_s, H_l) and K_s band observations from ZFOURGE, these fields have a wealth of ancillary multi-wavelength observations. Due to the high depth ($ABK_s < \sim 24.85\sigma$) of the ZFOURGE survey, Spitler et al. (2012) discovered the most distant candidate of a proto-cluster in the well studied COSMOS field.

Figure 1.8: Fraction of quiescent galaxies vs the local overdensity across redshifts from the ZFOURGE survey. Kawinwanichakij et al. (2017a) show that the difference in quenched fraction is high in both stellar mass bins ($\log M_*/M_\odot > 9.5$; filled circles and $\log M_*/M_\odot > 10.5$; unfilled squares). The quenched fraction increases with the local overdensity and with decreasing redshift. The difference between the quenched fraction between high and low mass galaxies in the highest density environments is largest at $z > 1.5$ and decreases by $0.5 < z < 1$. Credit: Kawinwanichakij et al. (2017a)

By studying the star formation activity in different environments across redshifts, Kawinwanichakij et al. (2017b) show that the quenched fraction of both high ($\log M_*/M_\odot > 10.5$) and low mass ($\log M_*/M_\odot > 9.5$) galaxies increases with the local overdensity across $0.5 < z < 2$. The overall quenched fraction also increases across cosmic time (from $z \sim 2$ to $z \sim 0.5$; Figure 1.8). The difference between the quenched fraction between high and low mass galaxies in the highest density environments is largest at $z > 1.5$ and decreases by $0.5 < z < 1$. In the high redshift universe $z > 1.5$, the effect of environment is evident

in the higher quenched fraction of both high and low stellar mass galaxies compared to their low density sample counterparts.

Figure 1.9: Evolution of the Stellar Mass Function (SMF) for quiescent (red; top row) and star-forming galaxies (blue; bottom row) in high (triangles) and low (diamonds) density environments from the ZFOURGE survey ($0.5 < z < 2.0$). The right most panels show a comparison SMF from the SDSS survey (Baldry et al., 2006). The SMF of the quiescent galaxies have a strong dependence on the environment across redshifts however, the SMF of start forming galaxies show no dependence on environment. Papovich et al. (2018)

The stellar mass function (SMF) of galaxies varies across environment across redshifts $0 < z < 1$ (Baldry et al., 2006; Peng et al., 2010; Tomczak et al., 2017). However, the consensus on the effect of environment in the high redshift universe is still unclear. Papovich et al. (2018) study the evolution of SMF of the quenched and star forming galaxies in across redshift $0 < z < 2$ from the ZFOURGE survey and find a strong dependence of the SMF of quenched galaxies on the local environment. The shape of the SMF of the total quenched galaxies closely tracks the SMF of quenched fraction in the highest density environment, indicating the role of environmental quenching in mainly determining the evolution of shape of SMF for the total quiescent galaxies.

These studies indicate a role of environment in the progression of star formation and quenching as early as $z \sim 2$. Although the medium band photometry in ZFOURGE provides accurate redshifts within 2 – 3% uncertainty (Nanayakkara et al., 2016), spectroscopic redshifts are required to accurately identify the large scale structure. Hence, we further explore the histories of star formation in a spectroscopically confirmed proto-cluster (from ZFIRE + ZFOURGE) and field galaxies to understand the role of environment in determining timescales of star formation and stellar mass growth at $z \sim 2$. We construct the SFHs by fitting the spectral energy distribution (SED) of galaxies using PROSPECTOR SED fitting code (Johnson et al., 2021; Leja et al., 2017). We present our results in Chapter 4 in this thesis.

1.3.3 PROSPECTOR SED Fitting

The history of a galaxy is encoded in its spectral energy distribution (SED). Analysing the SED of galaxies should tell us about the physical properties of galaxies and their evolutionary history. Modelling the galaxy SED can provide us fundamental information such as the star formation histories, stellar mass, star formation rates, metallicities and dust content of a galaxy (Conroy, 2013; Kriek et al., 2011; Leja et al., 2019, 2017; Robotham et al., 2020; Wuyts et al., 2011). Unsurprisingly, a large body of study has been conducted in the past decades, aimed at inferring the stellar populations and galaxy properties from the SED.

Figure 1.10: Transmission corresponding to the ZFOURGE (FourStar medium-bandwidth: $(j_1, j_2, j_3, H_s, H_l$ and K_s ; shown in shades of red) and some ancillary filters (shown in greys and transparent) available for the COSMOS field. The rich data set covers optical to Far-IR wavelengths. Credit: Straatman et al. (2016)

The rest-frame UV SED of a galaxy is affected by stellar populations ranging from young hot massive stars to post main sequence asymptotic giant branch (AGB) and horizontal branch (HB) stars. At $z = 2$, the UV rest-frame SED is redshifted to optical and NIR

making it more accessible with ground based imaging. In the COSMOS field, ZFOURGE photometry is supplemented by ancillary data providing observations in 37 bands ranging from UV to Far-IR from deep ground based and space based imaging. The large wavelength coverage ($\sim 3000 - 10^5 \text{\AA}$) accompanied by the finer sampling from medium band Near-IR imaging with FourStar makes an ideal data set to reconstruct star formation histories at $z = 2$.

We use PROSPECTOR to model the observed SED of a galaxy using python-Flexible Stellar Population Synthesis package (FSPS; (Conroy & Gunn, 2010)), MESA Isochrones and Stellar Tracks (MIST; Calzetti et al. 1994; Dotter 2016; Paxton et al. 2011, 2013, 2015), Calzetti dust attenuation models (Calzetti et al., 1994) and taking into account the nebular emission (CLOUDY; (Byler et al., 2018)) and dust re-radiation (da Cunha et al., 2008). From the modeled SED of galaxies, PROSPECTOR re-constructs the non parametric star formation histories in a series of piece-wise constant / step functions (with flexible time bins) within a Bayesian framework of prior probability distribution. We present our results of reconstructed SFHs using ZFIRE spectroscopic redshifts and ZFOURGE + literature photometry (Figure 1.10) and PROSPECTOR for galaxies at $z = 2$ in Chapter 3.

1.3.4 IllustrisTNG Cosmological Simulations

IllustrisTNG (Marinacci et al., 2018; Naiman et al., 2018; Nelson et al., 2018; Pillepich et al., 2018b; Springel et al., 2018) is a suit of cosmological magneto-hydrodynamical simulations of galaxy formation and evolution from soon after the Big Bang to the present day universe. Within the framework of the Λ CDM cosmological paradigm (Alves et al., 2016; Hinshaw et al., 2013), IllustrisTNG simulates the universe in different spatial and mass resolution. The IllustrisTNG model builds directly on Illustris simulations (Sijacki et al., 2015; Vogelsberger et al., 2014a,b) and includes a range of subgrid prescriptions to incorporate updated models of baryonic processes such as star formation, feedback, growth of blackholes, AGN feedback, galactic winds and chemical evolution (Pillepich et al., 2018a; Weinberger et al., 2017). In this thesis, we use the TNG100 simulation which simulates a periodic box of length 110 cMpc, 1820^3 dark matter particles and gas cells each of respective particle and cell mass of $7.5 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ and $1.4 \times 10^6 M_\odot$.

Using IllustrisTNG 300, Donnari et al. (2021) show that the fraction of quenched galaxies is dependent on the stellar mass of the galaxy, its position in the cosmic web and evolves

Figure 1.11: Evolution of quenched fraction of centrals (top) and satellites (bottom) vs galaxy stellar mass from TNG300 from $z = 3$ to $z = 0$. The quenched fraction of both centrals and satellites depend on the galaxy stellar mass across redshifts. The higher quenched fraction of lower mass galaxies in the satellite sample compared to the centrals indicates a role of environment in galaxy quenching even at $z = 3$. Credit: Donnari et al. (2021)

across cosmic time. They find that the quenched fraction of high mass galaxies is similar between central and satellite samples across redshifts and is mainly driven by the stellar mass and AGN feedback. The lack of low mass quenched centrals in contrast to a higher quenched fraction in satellites indicates the role of environment in quenching low mass satellite galaxies as early as $z \leq 3$ (Figure 1.11). The fraction of low mass quenched satellite galaxies also increases with the halo mass of the host halo and decreases with

cluster centric distance. These results are comparable to the results from Kawinwanichakij et al. (2017a), who also find a higher quenched fraction of low mass galaxies in high density environment compared to low density environments. However, Donnari et al. (2021) predict a higher quenched fraction of high mass centrals irrespective of environment across cosmic time compared to the observed quenched fractions in the ZFOURGE sample (Kawinwanichakij et al., 2017a). This difference in results could be driven by the different methods of sample selection or observational biases in ZFOURGE.

Figure 1.12: The stellar mass functions of red, blue and combined galaxy samples in the protocluster cores divided by the stellar mass function of the respective field galaxies. The three panels from left to right show SMFs of galaxies in all protocluster cores, protocluster cores with red central galaxy and blue central galaxies respectively from *IllustrisTNG* at $1 < z < 1.5$. Credit: Ando et al. (2022)

In a recent study, Ando et al. (2022) study the stellar mass function of galaxies in the core of protoclusters at $1 < z < 1.5$. They find a higher number of high mass red galaxies compared to the field sample in all selected protocluster core and significantly lower number of blue low mass galaxies in the protocluster core compared to the field sample (Figure 1.12). They also find that galaxies in the core of protoclusters with red centrals have a higher probability of having higher number of red galaxies compared to galaxies in core of protocluster with blue central. This indicates galaxy conformity or assembly bias. These results are comparable with the results from Papovich et al. (2018). Both studies find a higher fraction of massive red/quiescent galaxies in high density environment or protocluster core compared to low density/field environment. These results also have a similar top-heavy stellar mass function for the blue/star forming galaxies compared to red/quiescent galaxies.

The results discussed above make `IllustrisTNG` a robust tool providing a comparison of galaxy evolution theory to the observational results and a predictive tool to further understand and drive observational campaigns. However, most studies study either simulation or observations separately, making one-to-one comparison between the results difficult. Hence, we compare our observational results in Chapter 4 with `IllustrisTNG` to understand the evolution of star formation history of galaxies and the physical mechanisms driving the SFH. Furthermore, we explore within `IllustrisTNG`, the role of environment in the gas accretion history of galaxies in the early universe and report our results in Chapter 5.

1.4 Thesis Outline

This thesis aims to further explore whether the effect of environment is significant at $z \sim 2$ and what physical mechanisms drive the divergence of evolutionary history of cluster galaxies using the `ZFIRE` and `ZFOURGE` surveys and the publicly available `IllustrisTNG` cosmological simulations.

In Chapter 2, we present the observations of the global electron density of the protocluster galaxies in the UDS protocluster at $z = 1.62$ by measuring the ratio `[OII] ($\lambda 3727, 3729$)` doublet from the `ZFIRE` survey. We show for the first time, a tentative evidence of enhanced electron density in the low mass protocluster galaxies compared to the field galaxies. This Chapter is published in the *Astrophysical Journal* as Harshan et al. (2020)

In Chapter 3, we present the star formation histories of star forming protocluster and field galaxies in the COSMOS field constructed using SED fitting code `PROSPECTOR`. We find signs of star formation suppression in the most massive protocluster galaxies in the `ZFIRE` survey. We also present the comparison of star formation histories for cluster and field galaxies from `IllustrisTNG` cosmological simulations and find that the suppression of star formation in massive protocluster galaxies is a likely effect of lower gas fraction in massive protocluster galaxies since 1 Gyr in the age of the universe. This Chapter is published in the *Astrophysical Journal* as Harshan et al. (2021)

In Chapter 4 we explore the effect of environment on inflow rates of total gas in the early universe in `IllustrisTNG`. We find that the satellite galaxies in the high mass halos have rapidly declining total gas inflow rates after they enter the massive halo and as they

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

approach the halo center. On the other hand central galaxies continue to accrete more gas, with gas inflow rates increasing with increasing halo mass at $6 < z < 2$. This inequality in gas inflow rates drive galaxy quenching via gas starvation in cluster environment and leads to the build of the hot ICM observed in the local universe.

In Chapter 5, we present the conclusions and discuss future projects to further explore the role of environment in shaping the evolutionary history of galaxies.

Chapter 2

Measuring Electron Density with [O II] as a function of environment at $z = 1.62$

This chapter has been published as "ZFIRE: Measuring Electron Density with [O II] as a function of environment at $z = 1.62$ ", *The Astrophysical Journal*, 892, 77, 2020. The paper has been edited to match the style of the thesis for readability.

2.1 Abstract

The global star formation rates (SFR) of galaxies at fixed stellar masses increase with redshift and are known to vary with environment up to $z \sim 2$. We explore here whether the changes in the star formation rates also apply to the electron densities of the interstellar medium (ISM) by measuring the [O II] ($\lambda 3726, \lambda 3729$) ratio for cluster and field galaxies at $z \sim 2$. We measure a median electron density of $n_e = 366 \pm 84 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for six galaxies (with 1σ scatter = 163 cm^{-3}) in the UDS proto-cluster at $z = 1.62$. We find that the median electron density of galaxies in the UDS proto-cluster environment is three times higher compared to the median electron density of field galaxies ($n_e = 113 \pm 63 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and 1σ scatter = 79 cm^{-3}) at comparable redshifts, stellar mass and SFR. However, we note that a sample of six proto-cluster galaxies is insufficient to reliably measure the electron

density in the average proto-cluster environment at $z \sim 2$. We conclude that the electron density increases with redshift in both cluster and field environments up to $z \sim 2$ ($n_e = 30 \pm 1 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for $z \sim 0$ to $n_e = 254 \pm 76 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for $z \sim 1.5$). We find tentative evidence ($\sim 2.6\sigma$) for a possible dependence of electron density on environment, but the results require confirmation with larger sample sizes.

2.2 Introduction

Environment plays an extensive role in the evolution of galaxies. In the low-redshift universe ($z < 0.2$), high-density or cluster environment show a higher fraction of quenched galaxies and have galaxies with lower gas fractions compared to low-density or field environment (Barsanti et al., 2018; Blanton, 2006; Chung et al., 2009; Davies et al., 2019; Ellison et al., 2009; Grootes et al., 2018; Kauffmann et al., 2004; Koyama et al., 2013; Lewis et al., 2002a; Nichol et al., 2003). The frequency of lenticular and elliptical galaxies increases, and the frequency of spiral galaxies decreases with the local density indicating that environment affects the morphology of galaxies (Houghton, 2015; Paulino-Afonso et al., 2019; Sobral et al., 2011; van der Wel et al., 2009).

One possible explanation for the observed differences is that in high-density environments, the probability of galaxy-galaxy interactions (collisional and tidal interactions) increases. Through galaxy-galaxy interactions and interactions with the intra-cluster medium (ICM), star-forming disk galaxies transform into quenched spheroidals (Gnedin, 2003; Gunn & Gott $_{III}$, 1972; Moore et al., 1996; Smith et al., 2005).

As galaxies fall into the cluster, gas is stripped off through ram pressure stripping (Balogh et al., 2004; Brown et al., 2017; Cortese & Hughes, 2009; Gunn & Gott $_{III}$, 1972; Gupta et al., 2017; Hester, 2006; Nichols & Bland-Hawthorn, 2011), resulting in a gradual decline in the SFR as galaxies run out of their star formation fuel (strangulation; Bahé & McCarthy, 2015; Peng et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2018). Both simulations and observational studies find evidence of lower star formation in cluster galaxies compared to field galaxies up to $z \sim 2$ (Bahé et al., 2017; Darvish et al., 2017, 2016; Davies et al., 2019; Genel et al., 2018; Lewis et al., 2002b; Mcgee et al., 2011; Muzzin et al., 2012; Paccagnella et al., 2016; Paulino-Afonso et al., 2019; Rasmussen et al., 2012; Sobral et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015). At redshift $z = 1.62$, Tran et al. (2015) find systematically lower star formation rates in the

UDS (Ultra-Deep Survey) proto-cluster galaxies compared to the field galaxies, indicating a tentative effect of environment albeit not statistically significant.

Existing studies show that star-forming galaxies at redshift $z > 1$ have higher electron densities (Bian et al., 2010; Brinchmann et al., 2008; Shirazi et al., 2013) than their local counterparts. Electron densities of star-forming galaxies (SFGs) at $z > 1$ show weak correlation to global galaxy properties such as SFR and specific SFR (sSFR) (Kaasinen et al., 2017; Sanders et al., 2016; Shimakawa et al., 2015a) but no significant correlation with the ionization parameter (Shimakawa et al., 2015a). Because electron density of a galaxy varies with the SFR and sSFR (Kashino et al., 2017; Shimakawa et al., 2015a), variation of electron density with environment needs to be further explored.

The electron density measurements have been limited in galaxy clusters at $z < 0.2$, where the fraction of star-forming galaxies with emission lines is less than 10% (Davies et al., 2019; Lewis et al., 2002b). At $z \sim 0.5$, there are indications that the electron density depends on the local environment (Darvish et al., 2015; Sobral et al., 2015).

Darvish et al. (2015) find a negative correlation between the electron density of galaxies and their local environment density at $z \sim 0.5$. They find that electron density of low stellar mass galaxies in the filamentary structure is nearly 17 times lower than the electron density of field galaxies at the same stellar mass, SFR and sSFR.

Whereas at redshift $z > 1$, low signal-to-noise and insufficient sample size limits electron density measurements as a function of environment. With the advent of sensitive near-infrared and optical spectrographs, we can now probe the “redshift desert” ($1 < z < 3$ Harrison et al., 2017; Kacprzak et al., 2015; Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Steidel et al., 2014; Turner et al., 2017). Extensive studies are done on effects on environment on mass-metallicity relation, BPT diagnostics and star formation, however environmental effects on electron density studies still remain largely unexplored at higher redshifts ($z > 1$; Alcorn et al., 2019; Baldwin et al., 1981; Bassett et al., 2013; Kewley et al., 2015; Sobral et al., 2013; Tran et al., 2003; Turner et al., 2017; Wuyts et al., 2016) .

In this chapter, we investigate the effect of environment on the electron density in the UDS proto-cluster at redshift $z = 1.62$ (confirmed by Papovich et al., 2010; Tanaka et al., 2010; Tran et al., 2015). We use Keck-LRIS observations of the UDS proto-cluster taken as part of the ZFIRE survey (Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015). We estimate electron density using the [OII] ($\lambda 3726, \lambda 3729$) emission line doublet observations of the

UDS proto-cluster.

This chapter is organized as follows. In section 2.3, we describe the selected sample and data reduction process. We describe the method of electron density estimation in section 2.3.8 and state our results and analysis in section 4.4. We discuss and summarize our results in section 2.5 and 2.6.

For this work, we assume a flat Λ CDM cosmology with $\Omega_M = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, and $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. At redshift $z = 1.62$, $1''$ corresponds to an angular scale of 8.47 kpc.

2.3 DATA and Methodology

2.3.1 UDS Cluster

Our sample is sourced from the ZFIRE survey (Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015), which combines optical and near infrared spectroscopy of the proto-cluster in the UDS field at redshift $z_{cl} = 1.623$. The spectroscopic targets for the ZFIRE survey were selected from the UDS catalog (Williams et al., 2009) created as a part of the UKIRT Infrared Deep Sky Survey (UKIDSS), a near infrared imaging survey (Lawrence et al., 2007)¹.

The UDS proto-cluster, first reported by Papovich et al. (2010); Tanaka et al. (2010) is one of the first cluster used to demonstrate an increase in star formation density with local galaxy density (Tran et al., 2010). Still in its formative phase (Rudnick et al., 2012), the UDS proto-cluster has total star formation rate $> 1000 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Santos et al., 2014) and is an ideal candidate to study the variation of galaxy properties in high-density environments at $z > 1.5$.

Using the Keck-LRIS and Keck-MOSFIRE spectroscopy, 33 cluster members are identified in the redshift range $1.6118 \leq z_{\text{spec}} \leq 1.6348$. The median redshift of the proto-cluster is $z_{cl} = 1.623 \pm 0.0003$ and the cluster velocity dispersion is $\sigma_{cl} = 254 \pm 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Tran et al., 2015).

¹UDS proto-cluster also referred as XMM-LSS J02182-05102 or IRC 0218 (Tran et al., 2015) and CLG0218.3-0510 (Tran et al., 2010) and (Santos et al., 2014)

2.3.2 Optical Spectroscopy: Keck-LRIS

The optical observations were carried out as a part of the ZFIRE survey on the Low Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (LRIS; Oke et al., 1995) with a $5.5' \times 8'$ field of view and resolution of $0.135''$ per pixel. LRIS is equipped with red and blue cameras that can simultaneously cover a wavelength range of $3200 \text{ \AA} - 10000 \text{ \AA}$. The primary targets were candidate star-forming cluster galaxies identified by Tran et al. (2015), candidate Lyman-Break Galaxies at $z_{\text{phot}} > 1.35$, and [O II] emitters identified by Tadaki et al. (2012) from narrow-band imaging with magnitude $i_{AB} < 21$ mag. The secondary targets and mask fillers were galaxies with magnitude $21 < i_{AB} < 24$.

Observations were taken in excellent conditions with median seeing of about $0.6''$ on 19 and 20 October 2012 (NASA/Keck Program ID 48/2012B). Brightest cluster galaxies were targeted with high priority and observed in 3 out of 4 masks with 9×20 minute exposures. The fourth mask with low priority targets was observed for 5×20 minute exposures. In 4 masks, we observed a total of 136 galaxies.

The blue side of the spectrum covers a wavelength range $3800 \text{ \AA} < \lambda < 5800 \text{ \AA}$ using 600/4000 grism, and the red side $7000 \text{ \AA} < \lambda < 10000 \text{ \AA}$ using 600/10000 grating. A slit width of $1''$ results in a spectral resolution of 4.0 \AA and 4.7 \AA for the blue and red spectra respectively. With a resolution of 4.7 \AA in the observed frame, we get resolution of 1.79 \AA at $z = 1.62$ rest-frame. The [O II]($\lambda 3726, \lambda 3729$) doublet at $z \approx 1.62$ is observed at wavelength range approximately 9760 \AA to 9770 \AA and the 2.7 \AA rest-frame wavelength separation should be resolved with the 1.79 \AA resolution.

Spectra were reduced and sky subtracted using IRAF routines with custom software provided by D. Kelson (Kelson, 2003) for the red and blue sides separately. Cosmic ray rejection on the red side was done using *crutil* in IRAF. Median rectified science images after flat-fielding, wavelength calibration and sky line correction were used to create the combined images (Tran et al., 2015).

2.3.3 1-D Spectral Extraction

We extract 1-D spectra from the reduced red side of the 2D spectrum from LRIS-Keck by summing over the entire slit length and de-redshifting it to rest-frame using the pho-

ometric redshift taken from Tran et al. (2015). On the extracted initial 1-D spectrum, we fit a double Gaussian profile using the *optimize.curvefit* routine from the *scipy* library in Python to calculate spectroscopic redshift (z_{spec}). We de-redshift the spectrum in the initial step to provide a reliable set of first-guesses for the double gaussian parameters to the fitting routine *optimize.curvefit*.

To identify the position of the galaxy on the slit, we collapsed the spectrum in the selected wavelength window along the spatial direction and fit a Gaussian profile to the extracted spatial profile in the wavelength window which contains 3σ of the flux from [OII]doublet. This is done to reduce the contamination by the sky absorption lines very close to the [OII]emission lines. We take 3σ region around the centroid of the best-fit Gaussian profile as the position of galaxy along the slit and collapse the 2-D spectra in the selected spatial region (shown by purple lines in Fig. 2.2 and Fig. 2.3) along the wavelength direction to extract the 1-D spectrum for each galaxy. We visually inspect all apertures to ensure the inclusion of the both emission lines.

To minimize the effect of rotation and to remove spectral regions in the galaxy with blended [OII] lines, we modify the window in which we collapse the 2-D spectra for several galaxies. Purple lines in Fig. 2.2 (cluster galaxies) and Fig. 2.3 (field galaxies) show the window selected where 2-D spectra is collapsed to extract the 1-D spectra. We select a smaller aperture to avoid the regions of blended emission lines. In the region with blended [OII] lines, we cannot extract along rotational axis because it would introduce further uncertainties. Selecting small aperture will not affect the calculation of electron density as the doublet lines are visually congruent and thus the ratio of two emission lines would remain constant.

2.3.4 Emission Line Fitting

We use reduced red side of the 2-D spectrum comprising of wavelength range 7000 \AA to 10000 \AA of the Keck-LRIS data of the Ultra-Deep Survey (UDS) field using the method defined in Tran et al. (2015). We also use the redshift catalogs created by Tran et al. (2015).

While fitting the double Gaussian profile, we constrain the separation of the two peaks to be 2.7 \AA in the rest-frame as measured by atomic physics and require line widths of

the two lines to be the same. We tested the fitting by relaxing the constraint on the separation between the [O II] emission lines by 0.5 \AA but found no significant difference in the flux ratios. We weight the fit with the sky residual spectrum to reduce the effects of sky absorption. We measure the flux by integrating the fitted Gaussian profile within 3σ bound for each emission line and use the ratio of the flux for calculating the electron density. To determine the uncertainty in the electron density, we generate 500 Gaussian random spectra by perturbing the flux at each wavelength according to the sky noise at that wavelength. We calculate the [O II] doublet fluxes for each generated spectra and take the standard deviation of the created fluxes to be the 1σ error for each emission line flux.

2.3.5 Galaxy Selection

Due to the presence of many sky absorption lines in the rest-frame wavelength window near the [O II] emission lines, we select a sub-sample of galaxies by visually assigning each galaxy a quality flag $Q : 0 - 3$ that indicates the quality of the observation. Galaxies with barely visible emission lines or where lines are contaminated with sky absorption are rated 0. Galaxies with quality rating of 3 are the ones with clearly resolved doublet emission and minimal rotation in the selected aperture as shown in Fig. 2.2 and Fig. 2.3. For our study, we only consider the galaxies with $Q = 3$ rating, which results in a sample of 8 galaxies in the redshift regime of $1.3 \leq z \leq 1.7$ (1 Gyr). Out of the 8 galaxies, 6 are proto-cluster member galaxies because they lie in the redshift range $1.6118 \leq z \leq 1.6348$ (Tran et al., 2015) and rest are field galaxies.

Fig. 2.1 shows the SFR - stellar mass relation for the full sample, selected sub-sample with a quality rating of three and the comparison samples. Due to observational limitations and selection effects, all high redshift galaxies in the sample are biased towards galaxies with higher SFR (Tran et al., 2015). The high redshift sample spans the full range in SFR to the local SDSS sample. A student's t -test confirms the SFR and stellar mass distribution of the selected sample is consistent with the parent sample with p-values of 0.9 and 0.65. The SFR and stellar mass distribution of our selected cluster and field samples are also consistent with each other with a p-value of 0.9 and 0.7 respectively.

Figure 2.1: SFR vs Stellar Mass for the full sample at $1.3 < z < 1.7$ (black dots), selected cluster galaxies (red circles), selected field galaxies (blue circles), comparison sample at $z \sim 1.5$ from Kaasinen et al. (2017) (open diamonds) and the full SDSS sample (grey meshed contours). For high redshift samples, electron density is calculated with [O II] and for the local sample (SDSS), electron density is measured using [S II].

2.3.6 Local Comparison Data

Our Local comparison data has been taken from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) - DR7. Stellar masses, star formation rates and specific star formation rates have also been taken from the Galspec data of SDSS DR-7 (Abazajian et al., 2009; York, 2000) provided by MPA-JHU group. As the spectra is observed with $3''$ aperture and thus do not represent the entire galaxy, the total stellar mass are estimated using ugriz galaxy photometry (Brinchmann et al., 2004; Kauffmann et al., 2003; Tremonti et al., 2004). To minimize the aperture effects we select galaxies in $0.04 < z < 0.1$ (Kewley et al., 2005). We also reject AGNs from the sample following the Kauffmann et al. (2003) criteria using

optical line ratios $[\text{O III}]/\text{H}\beta$ and $[\text{N II}]/\text{H}\alpha$. Our Final sample includes 117000 galaxies in the local sample.

We select objects with signal-to-noise ratio $SNR > 3$ for emission lines $[\text{O III}] (\lambda 5007)$, $\text{H}\beta$, $[\text{N II}] (\lambda 6584)$, $\text{H}\alpha$, $[\text{S II}] (\lambda 6717, \lambda 6731)$. Because the $[\text{O II}]$ doublet is not resolved in the SDSS DR7, we calculate electron density with resolved $[\text{S II}] (\lambda 6717, \lambda 6731)$ doublet. We note that calculating electron density using $[\text{S II}]$ and $[\text{O II}]$ probes different parts of the HII regions of the galaxy (Kewley et al., 2019). However, Sanders et al. (2016) show that electron density calculated with $[\text{S II}]$ is comparable within the uncertainties in our data to the electron density calculated using $[\text{O II}]$ doublet.

To compare the SDSS local galaxy sample with the high redshift sample, we convert the total stellar masses of the low redshift sample from Kroupa (2001) to Chabrier (2003) initial mass function (IMF) with a constant scaling of 1.06 (Zahid et al., 2012).

2.3.7 Comparison Data at $1.5 < z < 2.6$

For comparison with redshift $z > 1$ we have collected three different data sets. $z \sim 1.5$ sample taken from Kaasinen et al. (2017) consists of galaxies from the COSMOS field between $1.4 < z < 1.7$. These galaxies are selected to be $[\text{O II}]$ emitters and were observed as part of the COSMOS $[\text{O II}]$ survey. The spectroscopic data has been taken on DEep Imaging Multi-Object Spectrograph (DEIMOS) on Keck II. We select 21 galaxies from the sample that was selected to be $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9.8$, $\text{SFR}_{\text{phot}} \geq 10 M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$ and $z(AB)$ magnitude $\lesssim 24$. The stellar mass has been converted to Chabrier IMF from Kroupa IMF for comparison with the other cluster sample and the specific Star Formation Rate (sSFR) has been calculated as $\text{SFR}/\text{Stellar mass}$ for each galaxy. Yuan et al. (2014) find that the structural over-densities in the COSMOS field is at $z = 2.09578 \pm 0.00578$. The Kaasinen et al. (2017) comparison data is outside of the redshift of number over-density in the COSMOS field, so we consider these as field galaxies.

The redshift $z = 2.3$ sample has been taken from MOSFIRE Deep Evolution Field survey (MOSDEF) Survey (Sanders et al., 2016). We take the $[\text{O II}] (\lambda 3726, \lambda 3729)$ doublet line ratio, stellar mass and SFR from Sanders et al. (2016). These observations were taken with MOSFIRE on GOODS-S and UDS-CANDELS field. The known over-densities in the UDS-CANDELS field is at $z = 1.62$ (Papovich et al., 2010; Tanaka et al., 2010) and

in GOODS-S is at $z = 3.5$ (Forrest et al., 2017). Hence, it is a reasonable assumption that $z \sim 2.3$ galaxies in these fields are field galaxies.

Our redshift $z \sim 2.5$ sample is taken from the plots in Shimakawa et al. (2015a). We take electron densities calculated for each $H\alpha$ emitter using the [O II] doublet emission line ratio and TEMDEN code distributed in the stsdas package and get a sample of 14 galaxies.

2.3.8 Electron Density

Emission lines originating from collisional excitation and de-excitation are affected by the electron density of the gas cloud. Thus, the electron density of a star-forming galaxy can be estimated using emission line fluxes of two energy levels from the same species that have similar excitation energy but different statistical weight and radiative transition probabilities (Osterbrock, 1989). The emission line flux ratio of the doublet only depends on the electron density and is modelled using collisional strengths and transition probabilities of each component using known atomic data.

We use the ratio of emission line doublets [S II] and [O II] lines as a function of electron density as derived by Sanders et al. (2016, equation 2.1). Sanders et al. (2016) assume a constant temperature of 10,000 K and a typical metallicity of H II regions. The errors in our electron density measurements are larger than the difference introduced by relaxing the constant temperature or metallicity assumption.

$$R(n_e) = a \frac{b + n_e}{c + n_e} \quad (2.1)$$

where, n_e is the electron density of the gas, and a, b, c hold the values listed in table 2.1.

$R(n_e)$	a	b	c
[O II]	0.3771	2,468	638.4
[S II]	0.4315	2,107	627.1

Table 2.1: Parameters relating Ratio of [O II] and [S II] doublets with electron density

Figure 2.2: Restframe spectra of cluster members within $1.6118 \leq z \leq 1.6348$. The top panel shows the 2D spectrum overlaid with the $6'' \times 6''$ HST(F125)/Subaru images. The purple lines show the window of spectra used to extract 1-D spectra. The green lines on the HST (F125)/Subaru (stacked v,b and i band images) images are the LRIS slits on the galaxy. The lower panel shows the extracted 1D spectrum inside the aperture shown with purple lines. The grey region show bootstrapped spectra and the black solid line is the median spectrum of the bootstrapped sample. The red dashed line is the fitted double Gaussian profile and the blue dashed line is the fitted Gaussian to each emission line. The merger pairs have been highlighted by orange box.

Figure 2.3: Restframe spectrum of field galaxies within $z \leq 1.6118$ and $z \geq 1.6348$. The top panel shows the 2D spectrum overlaid with the $6'' \times 6''$ HST /Subaru images. The purple lines show the window of spectra used to extract 1-D spectra. The green lines on the HST (F125)/Subaru (stacked v,b and i band images) images are the LRIS slits on the galaxy. The lower panel shows the extracted 1D spectrum inside the aperture shown with purple lines. The grey region show bootstrapped spectra and the black solid line is the median spectrum of the bootstrapped sample. The red line is the fitted double Gaussian profile. The merger pairs have been highlighted by orange box.

By inverting the above formula, the electron density of the gas can be calculated as:

$$n_e(R) = \frac{cR - ab}{a - R} \quad (2.2)$$

Electron densities derived using eq. 2.2 for both [OII] and [SII] are similar (Sanders et al., 2016).

To obtain the [OII] line ratio, we calculate the flux by integrating the fitted Gaussian profile within 3σ bound for each emission line and calculate the electron density using the equation 2.2. To determine the uncertainty in the electron density, we calculate electron density for each bootstrapped realizations of the observed spectra and take standard deviation of the distribution as 1σ error on the electron density. For sample sets, we consider the median and error on the median of electron density throughout the chapter.

Table 2.2: Cluster Galaxies

ID	RA ^a	DEC ^b	z _{spec} ^c	log $\frac{M_*}{M_\odot}$ ^d	log SFR ^e	log sSFR ^f	Ratio ^g	n _e ^h
39463	2:18:22.3	-5:10:34.5	1.6220	9.5	0.96	-8.60	1.429 ± 0.091	57 ⁺³² ₋₈₃
40243	2:18:28.0	-5:10:10.5	1.6220	9.61	0.45	-9.16	1.068 ± 0.199	384 ⁺²³² ₋₂₆₆
41297	2:18:24.2	-5:09:39.5	1.6221	9.93	1.15	-8.78	0.985 ± 0.148	491 ⁺³¹⁹ ₋₂₄₁
47191	2:18:29.8	-5:06:38.5	1.6331	9.94	0.45	-9.49	0.958 ± 0.056	474 ^{+0.47} ₋₁₄₇
46922	2:18:26.8	-5:06:49.4	1.6302	10.16	1.37	-8.79	1.284 ± 0.080	137 ⁺¹¹⁷ ₋₃₉
38455	2:18:26.2	-5:11:10.5	1.6238	10.87	1.09	-9.78	1.086 ± 0.080	349 ⁺¹¹⁹ ₋₇₁

Table 2.3: Field Galaxies

ID	RA ^a	DEC ^b	z _{spec} ^c	log $\frac{M_*}{M_\odot}$ ^d	log SFR ^e	log sSFR ^f	Ratio ^g	n _e ^h
44518	2:18:22.3	-5:10:34.5	1.4950	10.56	1.16	-9.40	1.381 ± 0.036	49 ⁺²⁸ ₋₂₄
49505	2:18:28.0	-5:10:10.5	1.4068	9.82	0.65	-9.17	1.257 ± 0.044	160 ⁺¹² ₋₅₉

Notes:^a Right ascension (J2000)^b Declination (J2000)^c spectroscopic redshift^d log stellar mass (from CANDELS survey)^e log star formation rate (from CANDELS survey) [M_⊙yr⁻¹]^f log specific Star formation rate (SFR/stellar mass) [yr⁻¹]^g Ratio of [O II] emission lines (λ3729/λ3726)^h Electron Density (cm⁻³) calculated as median of bootstrapped distribution of [O II] doublet ratio with 1σ errors

2.4 Results and Analysis

2.4.1 Electron Density and Environment

We measure the electron density for individual galaxies in the $z \sim 1.6$ UDS proto-cluster and field using the ratio of the [O II] (λ3726, λ3729) emission lines and equation 2.2. We measure the median electron density for the six cluster galaxies at $z \sim 1.62$ of $n_e = 366 \pm 84$ cm⁻³ and for the two field galaxies at similar redshift the average value of $n_e = 104 \pm 55$ cm⁻³ (Fig. 2.4). Although our field value is based on only two galaxies, we stress that the electron density is comparable to that measured by Kaasinen et al. (2017) for field galaxies $z \sim 1.5$ ($n_e = 114 \pm 28$ cm⁻³). Due to limitations in sample size for field galaxies, we combine our field galaxies from LRIS in the UDS field with field galaxies from Kaasinen et al. (2017). The median electron density for this combined sample is $n_e = 113 \pm 63$ cm⁻³.

We find tentative evidence of higher electron density in cluster galaxies compared to field galaxies ($\sim 2.6\sigma$). However, we are limited by the sample size and have significant scatter in the individual electron density measurements to make reliable conclusions (see Fig. 2.4b). We note that our sample is selected to be bright [O II] emitters, which biases our sample against cluster members that are undergoing environment dependent evolution and have lower star formation rates. We also note that 2 of the cluster galaxies and both field galaxies are merger components (Fig. 2.2, 2.3). However, we find no significant difference in their electron density compared to the rest of the sample.

2.4.2 Electron Density at $z \sim 0.0$ and $z \sim 1.6$

For comparison to the local $z \sim 0$ sample, we use the [S II] ($\lambda 6717, \lambda 6731$) ratio due to the lack of resolved [O II] ($\lambda 3726, \lambda 3729$) doublet in the SDSS. Sanders et al. (2016) show that electron densities measured with [O II] and [S II] are consistent, thus are comparable. To measure the redshift evolution of electron densities, we combine the cluster and field samples. The median electron density of the combined $z \sim 1.62$ sample is $254 \pm 76 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Whereas, the median electron density for the local SDSS sample is $n_e = 30 \pm 1 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, showing a nearly 8.5 times increase in the electron density at $z \sim 1.5 - 2$.

The increase in electron density with redshift when comparing $z \sim 0$ sample from SDSS to the $z \sim 1.5$ sample is significant at $\sim 3.8\sigma$ level. This result is consistent with other studies that also find a high electron density for galaxies in high redshift (Brinchmann et al., 2008; Sanders et al., 2016; Shirazi et al., 2013).

The high redshift samples are intrinsically biased towards galaxies with higher SFR compared to the SDSS sample. Kaasinen et al. (2017) find that the rising SFRs with redshift is responsible for the higher electron density of high redshift galaxies. We probe the redshift evolution of correlation of electron density and correct for the bias of the high redshift galaxies towards higher SFR by selecting the SDSS sample in the same SFR range as our $z = 1.6$ sample ($2.8 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1} \leq \text{SFR} \leq 23.6 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$). The median electron density of the SFR matched SDSS sample is $n_e = 31 \pm 9 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. We find no significant change in the electron density of the local SDSS sample even after matching with SFR of our high redshift sample (further discussed in section 2.4.4).

2.4.3 Electron Density Vs Stellar Mass

We investigate how the electron density varies with the stellar mass of the galaxy (Fig 2.4). The median electron density for the UDS proto-cluster sample at median $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.93$ with 1σ scatter of 0.43 is $n_e = 366 \pm 84 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. For our two field galaxies with average $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 10.19$ with 1σ scatter of 0.37, the average electron density is $n_e = 104 \pm 55 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. At similar stellar mass range, the median electron density of cluster galaxies is at a $\sim 2.6\sigma$ difference to field galaxies, within the limitation of our sample size.

We bin our sample into two stellar mass bins of $\log(M_*/M_\odot) \leq 10$ and $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10$ (Fig. 2.5). The high mass bin (4 galaxies) of the cluster sample at $z = 1.62$ has a median mass of $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 10.5$ and median electron density of $n_e = 243 \pm 74 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and the low mass bin (2 galaxies) with median mass of $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.77$, have median electron density of $n_e = 429 \pm 116 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Due to the limited number of field galaxies in our sample, we compare our results with the field galaxy sample from Kaasinen et al. (2017) at $z = 1.5$. The median stellar mass of the high stellar mass bin in Kaasinen et al. (2017) is $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 10.28$ and electron density is $n_e = 218 \pm 19 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Similarly, the low stellar mass bin in Kaasinen et al. (2017) has a median mass of $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.8$ and median electron density of $n_e = 113 \pm 46 \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

We find no significant correlation ($< 2\sigma$) between the electron density and stellar mass. Although, we see a reversal in trend between cluster galaxies at $z = 1.6$ and comparison field sample at $z = 1.5$ (Kaasinen et al., 2017), the differences are within 2σ level and hence not statistically significant. Our result is consistent with other high redshift observations (Kaasinen et al., 2017; Sanders et al., 2016; Shimakawa et al., 2015a).

2.4.4 Electron Density Vs Star Formation Rate

We analyze the correlation of electron density with the star formation rate (SFR) and specific star formation rate (sSFR) in Fig. 2.6. At $z = 1.6$, the cluster and field sample have a median SFR of $10.6 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ with 1σ spread of $7.8 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $9.4 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ with 1σ spread of $7.1 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ respectively. We continue to find tentative dependence of electron density on environment in cluster and field sample at $z \sim 1.6$, however, we are limited by large associated errors and small sample size. We also find no significant correlation between the SFR and electron density in our $z = 1.6$ sample, consistent with results from

Figure 2.4: Ratio of [OII] and [SII] doublet (a) used to calculate electron density and Electron density (n_e) (b) as a function of stellar mass ($\log(M_*/M_\odot)$). Cluster and field galaxies at $z \sim 1.6$ shown by red filled and blue unfilled markers respectively. We compare our results with three different comparison data sets of field galaxies at $z \sim 2.3$, $z \sim 2.5$ and $z \sim 1.5$, with green, pink and grey unfilled symbols respectively. The meshed grey contours show the electron density for the SDSS sample. Grey shaded area shows the upper-limit of non-detection for the UDS proto-cluster sample.

Figure 2.5: Electron density n_e as a function of stellar mass ($\log(M_*/M_\odot)$) for the low mass ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) \leq 10$) and high mass ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10$) bins plotted against the median stellar mass of the binned galaxy sample. Cluster galaxies at $z \sim 1.6$ shown by red filled circles. We compare our results with three different comparison data sets of field galaxies at $z \sim 2.3$, $z \sim 2.5$ and $z \sim 1.5$, with green, pink and grey unfilled symbols respectively. The meshed grey contours show the electron density distribution for the SDSS sample. These results show no significant variation between electron density of cluster galaxies at $z \sim 1.6$ with high redshift field comparison samples.

Sanders et al. (2016) and Kewley et al. (2013). Shimakawa et al. (2015a) find a positive correlation between the electron density and sSFR at a 4σ level, albeit with large error bars and limited sample at $z \sim 2.5$.

For comparison with the local SDSS star-forming galaxies and to correct for the bias of the high redshift galaxies towards higher SFR compared to local SDSS galaxies, we select SDSS sample in the same SFR range as our $z = 1.6$ sample ($2.8 M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1} \leq \text{SFR} \leq 23.6 M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$). The median electron density of the SFR matched SDSS sample is $n_e = 31 \pm 9 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The electron density of SFR matched SDSS sample by Kaasinen et al. (2017) is $n_e = 98 \pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, similar to the electron density of $z \sim 1.5$ sample in their study. Kaasinen et al. (2017) selected the SFR matched SDSS sample by matching the distribution in the SFR between $z \sim 1.5$ and the local sample. However, our limited sample at $z \sim 1.6$ does not allow us to match the distribution of SFRs. The different SFR distribution (different medians) between the SFR matched SDSS sample and our $z \sim 1.6$ sample can contribute to the observed difference in their median electron density.

Table 2.4: Median Electron Density Measurements

Sample Set	redshift z	$n_e(\text{cm}^{-3})$
UDS proto-cluster	1.62	366 ± 84
Field sample	~ 1.5	104 ± 55
Field sample + Kaasinen et al. (2017)	~ 1.5	113 ± 63
Full sample	~ 1.5	254 ± 76
SDSS	< 0.1	30 ± 1
Kaasinen et al. (2017)	1.5	114 ± 28
Sanders et al. (2016) ([OII])	2.3	225^{+119}_{-4}

2.5 Discussion

We measure the electron density for six galaxies in the UDS proto-cluster at $z \sim 1.6$ and compare it with field galaxies at $z \sim 1.5$. We find that cluster galaxies have higher electron density compared to field galaxies ($\sigma \sim 2.6$). However, the small sample size and large scatter in individual electron densities make our conclusions tentative only. Our results are different to Kewley et al. (2015), who do not find significant effect of environment on electron density in the COSMOS proto-cluster at $z \sim 2.0$. We note the difference in methods for calculating electron densities by Kewley et al. (2015), who use [SII] emission lines and stacking of 1D spectra to increase the SNR.

Figure 2.6: Ratio of [OII] or [SII] doublet (upper panels) and Electron density (n_e) (lower panels) as a function of log star formation rate ($M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$) (left) and specific star formation rate (yr^{-1}) (right). Cluster and field galaxies at $z \sim 1.6$ shown by red filled and blue unfilled markers respectively. We compare our results with three different comparison data sets of field galaxies at $z \sim 2.3$, $z \sim 2.5$ and $z \sim 1.5$, with green, pink and grey unfilled symbols respectively. The meshed grey contours show the electron density distribution for the SDSS sample. We measure no correlation of electron density with the SFR or sSFR and find no significant variation between electron density of cluster galaxies at $z \sim 1.6$ with high redshift field samples.

In contrast to our results, by stacking galaxies in stellar mass, SFR and sSFR bins Darvish et al. (2015) measure ≈ 17 times lower electron density for galaxies in a filamentary region (≈ 5 times denser than the field) compared to field galaxies at $z \sim 0.5$. However, their individual electron density measurements have significantly large errors and scatter. Moreover, we are looking at environmental dependence on the electron density at $z \sim 1.5$ where environmental effects are less significant as opposed to $z \sim 0.5$ (Alcorn et al., 2019; Gupta et al., 2018; Kewley et al., 2013; Tran et al., 2015).

We observe redshift evolution of the electron density between the local SDSS sample and $z \sim 1.6$ sample after matching the stellar mass, SFR and sSFR range of the two samples. We find that electron density increases by a factor of ≈ 8.5 from $z \sim 0$ to ~ 1.5 , even with our limited sample size. Kaasinen et al. (2017) find that after matching the SFR distribution between the local SDSS galaxies with galaxies at $z \sim 1.5$, difference between the electron density of low and high-redshift sample disappears. Different methods for selecting SFR-matched sample from local and $z \sim 1.6$ sample might be responsible for this observed difference (Section 2.4.4).

Our work indicates no apparent correlation between the electron density and the stellar mass, SFR or specific SFR of galaxies at $z = 1.62$. Cluster galaxies in the low stellar mass bin have slightly higher in electron density compared to field galaxies, however the difference is at $< 2\sigma$ significance (Fig. 2.5). We also find a redshift evolution of electron density from $z \sim 0$ to $z \sim 1.6$. The higher SFR and gas surface density of galaxies at $z \sim 1.6$ compared to galaxies in the local universe might be responsible for ≈ 8.5 times increase in the electron density of galaxies at $z \sim 1.6$ (Madau & Dickinson, 2014).

By analyzing the Subaru and HST imaging, we find that both field galaxies and two of six cluster galaxies (Fig. 2.2, 2.3) in our sample are part of merger pairs. Within the small sample, the electron density of mergers are comparable to the rest of the sample at $z \sim 1.5$. Merging galaxies have SFRs and electron densities comparable to the non-merger sample. Mergers have ≈ 1 dex lower sSFR than the rest because of their higher stellar masses. However, we require larger sample of mergers to fully investigate the role of mergers on the electron density of galaxies.

Electron density measured using different species ratios probe different parts of the HII regions in the galaxy. In a recent paper Kewley et al. (2019) find that electron densities measured using [SII] ratios would probe the outer parts of the nebulae in the high pressure

clumps unlike [OII] ratio. However, Sanders et al. (2016) find no significant difference between electron densities calculated using [OII] and [SII].

Studies like ours that measures the electron density in intermediate and high redshift universe remain challenging. The large sample of proto-clusters at $z > 1.0$ needs to be explored to fully understand the role of environment on the electron density. Also, we currently do not understand how diffused-ionised gas emission effects the electron density measurements from the integrated emission line studies (Shapley et al., 2019). Near-infrared spectrographs on next generation space and ground based telescopes would be able to provide sub-kpc scale resolution on intermediate and high- z galaxies to further analyze the redshift and environment dependent evolution of the electron density galaxies.

2.6 Summary

We analyze how environment affects the electron density of galaxies in the UDS proto-cluster (IRC0218) at $z = 1.6$. We use spectroscopic data from LRIS on Keck1 taken as part of the ZFIRE survey and calculate the electron density using the ratio of optical emission lines [OII] ($\lambda 3726, \lambda 3729$). We identify six cluster members ($1.6118 < z_{spec} < 1.6348$) and two field galaxies with resolved [OII]. We compare our results with the SDSS DR7 emission line catalogue from the local universe, and other field samples at $z \sim 1.5 - 2.5$ from literature. We note that our $z = 1.6$ sample is biased towards galaxies with higher SFR compared to local SDSS sample.

With our limited sample at $z = 1.62$, we measure the median electron density of the cluster galaxies to be $366 \pm 84 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $104 \pm 55 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the field sample. Despite the higher electron density measured in the cluster, the difference is statistically insignificant due to high associated errors and limited sample size. We find a large scatter in the electron density of galaxies, similar to the local SDSS and other $z > 1.5$ samples.

We find that the average electron density increases with increasing redshift. The median electron density in local SDSS star-forming galaxies is measured as $30 \pm 1 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and the median electron density of $z = 1.62$ sample is $254 \pm 76 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. We also find no significant correlation between the electron density and stellar mass (Fig. 2.4 and Fig. 2.5), SFR and sSFR (Fig. 2.6), in agreement to other studies at $z > 1.5$.

CHAPTER 2. MEASURING ELECTRON DENSITY WITH [OII] AS A FUNCTION OF ENVIRONMENT AT $Z = 1.62$

To summarize, we find tentative evidence of effect of environment on the electron density of galaxies at $z = 1.62$. However we note that we are limited by a small sample size of eight galaxies. Further investigation of electron density with a larger sample for clusters at $z > 1.0$ and higher SNR spectra are needed to establish conclusively any possible effect of environment on the electron density.

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Chapter 3

The Beginning of the End for Massive Galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and Why Environment Matters

This chapter has been published as "ZFIRE: The Beginning of the End for Massive Galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and Why Environment Matters." The Astrophysical Journal, 919, 57, 2021. The paper has been edited to match the style of the thesis for readability.

3.1 Abstract

We use ZFIRE and ZFOURGE observations with the Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) fitting tool PROSPECTOR to reconstruct the star formation histories (SFHs) of proto-cluster and field galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and compare our results to the TNG100 run of the IllustrisTNG cosmological simulation suite. In the observations, we find that massive proto-cluster galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) form $45 \pm 8\%$ of their total stellar mass in the first 2 Gyr of the universe compared to $31 \pm 2\%$ formed in the field galaxies. In both observations and simulations, massive proto-cluster galaxies have a flat/declining SFH with decreasing redshift compared to rising SFH in their field counterparts. Using IllustrisTNG, we find that massive galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$) in both environments are on average ≈ 190 Myr older than low mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9 - 9.5$). However, the difference in

mean stellar ages of cluster and field galaxies is minimal when considering the full range in stellar mass ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) \geq 9$). We explore the role of mergers in driving the SFH in *IllustrisTNG* and find that massive cluster galaxies consistently experience mergers with low gas fraction compared to other galaxies after 1 Gyr from the Big Bang. We hypothesize that the low gas fraction in the progenitors of massive cluster galaxies is responsible for the reduced star formation.

3.2 Introduction

Star formation is one of the key processes that drives the evolution of galaxies. Understanding when, where, and how stars are formed remains one of the major goals of extragalactic astronomy. Internal processes like supernovae and Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN) feedback (Bower et al., 2006; Croton et al., 2007; Efstathiou, 2000; Fabian, 2012; Somerville, 2008) and dynamical instabilities (Kormendy & Ho, 2013) regulate star formation in a galaxy. Likewise, external physical processes such as galaxy-galaxy interactions, ram pressure stripping (Cortese et al., 2010; Gunn & Gott_{III}, 1972), harassment, strangulation (Balogh et al., 2000; Moore et al., 1998), gas accretion (Kacprzak, 2017; Tumlinson et al., 2017) and tidal interactions also leave their imprint on the star formation history of each galaxy.

Galaxies falling into the cluster potential are subjected to interactions with other galaxies and the Intra-cluster Medium (ICM). Galaxy-galaxy mergers can trigger a star formation phase in the galaxy by funneling the flow of atomic gas into the core of the galaxies (Barnes & Hernquist, 1996; Ellison et al., 2010; Springel et al., 2005). Processes like ram pressure stripping, tidal interactions and harassment deplete the star formation fuel of a galaxy. These processes cumulatively lead to a gradual decline of star formation in galaxies in the cluster environment and can be observed as the higher fraction of quenched early type galaxies in the local universe ($z < 0.1$) (Balogh et al., 2000; Barsanti et al., 2018; Kauffmann et al., 2004; Paccagnella et al., 2016; Pasquali et al., 2019; Presotto et al., 2012; Schaefer et al., 2019; Wetzel et al., 2013).

While the effect of environment on the star formation in galaxies is well studied at $z \sim 0$, the same remains ambiguous at higher redshift. Some studies find lower star formation rates in cluster members compared to isolated field galaxies at $z \sim 1$ similar to what we

observe in the local universe (Old et al., 2020; Patel et al., 2011; Popesso et al., 2012; Vulcani et al., 2010; Williams et al., 2009). Whereas others find a reversal in this trend (Allen et al., 2016; Elbaz et al., 2007, 2011; Muzzin et al., 2012; Peng et al., 2010; Tran et al., 2010; Wetzel et al., 2012). It is still ambiguous when the environmental effects leads to significant suppression in the star formation rates of galaxies in dense regions.

The ZFIRE survey (Nanayakkara et al., 2016) targets proto-cluster galaxies at $z \sim 2$ and 1.6 selected from the ZFOURGE survey in the COSMOS and UDS fields to identify the onset of environmental effects on galaxy properties. Environmental effects on inter stellar medium (ISM) properties, such as gas phase metallicity and electron density, appear to be not significant till $z \sim 1.5$ (Alcorn et al., 2019; Kacprzak et al., 2015; Kewley et al., 2016) similar to the results from IllustrisTNG (Gupta et al., 2018). However, at $z = 1.6$, there is tentative evidence of effect of environment on the star formation rates of galaxies in the proto-cluster core (Tran et al., 2015) and electron density (Harshan et al., 2020).

Observations at low redshift ($z < 1$) find that the massive galaxies form their stars earlier and more rapidly compared to the low mass galaxies (Brinchmann et al., 2004; Carnall et al., 2018; Cimatti et al., 2006; Cowie, 1996; Thomas et al., 2005, 2010; Treu et al., 2005; Webb et al., 2020). Massive galaxies form the majority of their stars within the first 1-2 Gyr of cosmic history and start to quench as early as $z \sim 3$ (Forrest et al., 2018; Glazebrook et al., 2017; Straatman et al., 2016). Similarly, galaxies in high density environments form the majority of their stars earlier compared to the field galaxies and are on average 1-2 Gyr older than the field galaxies (Thomas et al., 2005). However, at higher redshift ($z \sim 1$), the age difference between cluster and field galaxies is less significant, $\lesssim 0.5$ Gyr (Webb et al., 2020). The cumulative effect of environment leading to galaxy quenching could be driving the redshift evolution of age difference between cluster and field galaxies.

Cosmological simulations and semi-analytic models (Bahé et al., 2017; De Lucia et al., 2012; Donnari et al., 2020, 2021; Furlong et al., 2015; Tremmel et al., 2019) similarly show higher quenched fractions in the cluster members compared to the field sample at $z = 0$ to $z = 2$. In the IllustrisTNG simulations, Donnari et al. (2020, 2021) find a higher quenched fraction in the low mass satellite galaxies compared to low mass centrals indicating a role of environment in quenching of low mass galaxies. On the other hand, high mass galaxies, whether they are centrals or satellites, have high quenched fractions indicating effects of both secular and environmental quenching mechanisms.

One straightforward way of studying the evolution of galaxies is to study the star formation histories (SFH) of galaxies. The reconstruction of SFHs allows us to study the stellar mass assembly and gas accretion histories of galaxies over cosmic time. However, inferring the SFHs from observables is an extremely complex process. Star formation histories can be reconstructed by fitting the spectral energy distributions (SED) models for different stellar populations to the observed photometry of galaxies. We have moved from a simple exponential to more complex functional forms (Buat et al., 2008; Maraston et al., 2010; Papovich et al., 2011) such as lognormals (Abramson et al., 2015; Carnall et al., 2018; Gladders et al., 2013) even to non parametric SFHs (Chauke et al., 2018; Fernandes et al., 2005; Kelson et al., 2014; Leja et al., 2017; Ocvirk et al., 2006; Robotham et al., 2020).

In this chapter, we will study the effect of environment on the star formation histories of galaxies in a COSMOS proto-cluster at $z = 2.095$ (Spitler et al., 2012; Yuan et al., 2014). We present the first measurement of SFHs in the proto-cluster environment at $z = 2$. We use the SED fitting code PROSPECTOR (Johnson et al., 2021; Leja et al., 2017) in conjunction with the extensive photometric data from the ZFOURGE survey (Straatman et al., 2016) and spectroscopic redshifts from the ZFIREsurvey (Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015) to reconstruct the SFHs. We study the correlation of SFHs with the stellar mass and the environment of the galaxy. We then compare our results from observations to the SFHs retrieved from the cosmological hydrodynamical simulations *IllustrisTNG*.

This chapter is organised as follows. In Section 3.3.1 we describe the data used with PROSPECTOR to create SFHs as described in Section 3.3.2. In Section 3.3.3 we describe the SFHs from *IllustrisTNG*. In Sections 4.4 and 4.5 we state our results and discussion and in Section 4.6 summarise the results. For this work, we assume a flat Λ CDM cosmology with $\Omega_M = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, and $H_0 = 69.6 \text{ kms}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

3.3 Methodology

3.3.1 ZFIRE and ZFOURGE Surveys

Our observation sample is taken from the ZFOURGE - Fourstar Galaxy Evolution Survey (Straatman et al., 2016), a deep, UV to FIR, medium-band survey, completed on the FourStar instrument (Persson et al., 2013) on the Magellan Telescope. It reaches depth

of ~ 26 mag in J_1, J_2, J_3 and ~ 25 mag in H_s, H_l, K_s bands. ZFOURGE spans the Cosmic Evolution Survey field (Scoville et al., 2007, COSMOS) that covers the spectroscopically confirmed proto-cluster at $z_{cl} = 2.09 \pm 0.00578$ (Spitler et al., 2012; Yuan et al., 2014). The ZFOURGE survey reaches 80% completeness till 25.5 AB magnitude in K_s band, which corresponds to $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9$ at $z = 2$ (Straatman et al., 2016). The photometric redshifts and stellar mass catalogs were created with the publicly available SED fitting codes EAZY (Brammer et al., 2008) and FAST (Kriek et al., 2009). The UV-IR star formation rates were derived in Tomczak et al. (2016).

The ZFIRE survey (Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015) is the spectroscopic follow-up of ZFOURGE survey using Keck-MOSFIRE (McLean et al., 2010, 2012). The spectroscopic sample was selected based on the ZFOURGE photometric redshifts of the proto-cluster discovered at $z \sim 2$ (Spitler et al., 2012). The estimated halo mass of the $z = 2.09$ COSMOS proto-cluster based on the velocity dispersion measurements has virial mass in range $M_{vir} = 10^{13.5 \pm 0.2} M_\odot$. More than two emission lines: $H\alpha, H\beta, [NII]$ or $[OIII]$ observed in H and K bands are used to measure the spectroscopic redshifts.

We select 57 cluster members in the COSMOS proto-cluster between redshift $2.08 < z < 2.12$ (Spitler et al., 2012; Tran et al., 2015; Yuan et al., 2014) and 130 field galaxies in $1.8 < z < 2.5$. Figure 3.1 shows the spatial distribution of the spectroscopically confirmed proto-cluster (red circles) and field (blue diamonds) across the COSMOS field. This distribution is not a depiction of true distribution of galaxies in $1.8 < z < 2.5$ in the ZFOURGE survey, but an effect of the observational strategy used in the spectroscopic follow-up for the ZFIRE survey (Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Yuan et al., 2014). Figure 3.2 shows the SFR-Stellar mass relation of the selected cluster (red circles) and field (blue diamonds) galaxies. Due to the observational limit on the $H\alpha$ flux, ZFIRE observations have a SFR lower limit of $0.8 M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$ (Yuan et al., 2014).

3.3.2 Star Formation Histories using PROSPECTOR SED Fitting

PROSPECTOR is a SED fitting tool used to derive physical properties of galaxies using photometry and spectra. PROSPECTOR uses the python-Flexible Stellar Population Synthesis package (Conroy & Gunn, 2010) and we use the MESA Isochrones and Stellar Tracks (MIST; Calzetti et al. (1994); Dotter (2016); Paxton et al. (2015) and takes into account the nebular emission (Byler et al., 2018), dust attenuation and re-radiation. It

Figure 3.1: Spatial Distribution of spectroscopically confirmed ZFIRE proto-cluster (red circle) and field (blue diamonds) galaxies in the COSMOS field at $z \sim 2$. The dashed rings indicate the peaks in surface density as identified by Yuan et al. (2014) and Spitler et al. (2012).

uses Bayesian inference framework to derive non parametric formulation of star formation histories using simple piece-wise constant functions. PROSPECTOR also allows for adaptive time binning for the SFHs with varying number of bins. It fits non-parametric SFHs by calculating the fraction of stellar mass formed in a particular time bin (Leja et al., 2019). We use Calzetti dust attenuation model (Calzetti et al., 1994), Chabrier IMF (Chabrier, 2003) and WMAP9 (Hinshaw et al., 2013) cosmology throughout the analysis.

We use PROSPECTOR on the 5 NIR medium-band photometry from the ZFOURGE survey along with 32 other UV-MIR photometric bands from the legacy data sets covering the wavelength regime of $0.4448 - 7.9158 \mu m$ (Straatman et al., 2016) for the cluster and field galaxies and spectroscopic redshifts from ZFIRE. We use a uniform prior across all stellar mass bin allowing us to do a comparative analysis of the SFHs. We keep 9 free parameters: stellar mass, stellar and gas-phase metallicity, dust attenuation and five independent non-

Figure 3.2: Stellar Mass - SFR relation of selected cluster (red circle) and field (blue diamonds) galaxies from ZFIRE. Stellar Mass and the UV-IR SFR has been taken from the ZFOURGE survey (Straatman et al., 2016; Tomczak et al., 2016)

parametric SFH bins. We choose the age bins to roughly match the time resolution of the *IllustrisTNG* cosmological simulation (Nelson et al., 2019) (described in Section 3.3.3). We use the following 5 time bins : 0-200 Myr, 200-400 Myr, 400-600 Myr, 600-1000 Myr and 1000- $(t_{univ} - 1000)/2$ Myr. With the prescribed age bins, PROSPECTOR fits for 6 SFH bins, but the additional constraint on fractional stellar mass to be summed to one results in only five independent SFH bins. Our results do not depend significantly on the choice of age bins.

The stellar mass of galaxies calculated from PROSPECTOR agrees reasonably (~ 0.5 dex) with the stellar masses from FAST from the ZFOURGE survey (Cohn et al., 2018). There is a reasonable agreement between the two with higher stellar masses of galaxies from PROSPECTOR as seen and discussed in Leja et al. (2019). This is speculated to be a result of different assumptions and models for SFHs in FAST and PROSPECTOR.

Figure 3.3: Examples of observed ZFOURGE photometry (orange squares) fitted with PROSPECTOR to get modelled photometry (purple diamonds) and modelled SED (purple line). The stamps show $1.5'' \times 1.5''$ RGB (F160W, F814W, F606W) images of galaxies from 3D-HST survey. The error bars on the observed photometry are smaller than the orange squares.

We fit SEDs of 57 cluster galaxies in the redshift regime $2.08 \leq z \leq 2.12$ and 130 field galaxies in the redshift regime $1.8 \leq z \leq 2.5$ using the ZFIRE spectroscopic redshifts. We extract the posterior distribution of the stellar mass, five SFHs time bins and take the 16th, 50th and 84th percentile of the distribution from PROSPECTOR. Figure 3.3 shows the SED fits of four galaxies. The model spectrum (solid purple line) and the model photometry (purple diamonds) are well fitted to the observed photometry (orange squares).

We divide the proto-cluster and field galaxies into four stellar mass bins: $9-9.5 \log(M_*/M_\odot)$, $9.5-10 \log(M_*/M_\odot)$, $10-10.5 \log(M_*/M_\odot)$ and $\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$. We create boost-rapped samples of individual SFHs in each stellar mass bins and present the medians and errors in the median in Figure 3.4.

3.3.3 Star Formation Histories from IllustrisTNG

IllustrisTNG is a suite of magneto-hydro-dynamical cosmological simulations based on the Λ -CDM cosmology (Marinacci et al., 2018; Naiman et al., 2018; Nelson et al., 2018; Pillepich et al., 2018a; Springel et al., 2018). IllustrisTNG extends the Illustris framework with kinetic black hole feedback, magneto-hydrodynamics, and a revised scheme for galactic winds, among other changes (Pillepich et al., 2018a; Weinberger et al., 2017).

In this chapter we use the TNG100 box with $L_{\text{box}} = 110.7 \text{ cMpc}$, and total volume $\sim 10^6 \text{ Mpc}^3$, to map the star formation rate histories of the cluster and field galaxies. The data of TNG100 have been made publicly available and is described by Nelson et al. (2019). The TNG100 simulation has a baryonic mass resolution of $m_b = 1.4 \times 10^6 M_\odot$. This resolution provides about 1000 stellar particles per galaxy for a galaxy with stellar mass $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9$, and proportionally more stellar particles for more massive galaxies. The TNG100 simulation also provides a range of halo masses from $10^9 \leq M_{200} \leq 10^{15}$, making this an ideal simulation for our analysis. For the entire analysis, we constrain our galaxies to have $\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 9$ at redshift $z = 2$.

The COSMOS protocluster from observations has $M_{\text{vir}} = 10^{13.5 \pm 0.2} M_\odot$ Yuan et al. (2014). Thus to match the protoclusters from observations, we define galaxy clusters as halos of total mass $M_{200} \geq 10^{13} M_\odot$ at $z = 2$ and the galaxies residing in the cluster halo except the most massive central galaxy are satellites. We identify galaxies that reside in halos of total mass $M_{200} < 10^{13} M_\odot$ at $z = 2$ as field galaxies. In this analysis, galaxies are

subhalos from the SUBFIND catalog with stellar mass $\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 9$ (in twice the half mass radius) at $z = 2$. We select galaxies (centrals+satellites) associated with the cluster halos as cluster members whereas the field sample is made of galaxies associated with the field halos. Donnari et al. (2019) show that the main sequence of star forming galaxies in *IllustrisTNG* is lower compared to the observationally-inferred star formation main sequence at $z > \sim 0.75$. Hence, to match the SFR threshold from the observations to simulations we do the following. We calculate the difference between the star formation main sequence at $z = 2$ from Tomczak et al. (2016) and the observational SFR threshold of $0.8 M_* \text{yr}^{-1}$ (Section 3.3.1) as a function of stellar mass. We subtract the calculated difference from the median SFR-stellar mass relation of the entire sample of TNG100 and get a SFR threshold of $0.4 M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$. Following this selection criteria, we get a sample of 232 cluster galaxies from 24 cluster halos and 9577 field galaxies.

We use the SUBLINK algorithm which tracks the merger histories of the galaxies to quantitatively follow the evolution of galaxies (Rodriguez-Gomez et al., 2015). We trace the SFRs of the cluster and field galaxies in the four defined stellar mass bins from $z = 2$ to $z = 6$. Figure 3.6 shows the distribution of the SFHs of the selected sample sets.

3.4 Results

In this Section we show and discuss the SFHs of galaxies in a proto-cluster at $z \sim 2$ derived from SED fitting of observations with PROSPECTOR. We compare our results with predictions from *IllustrisTNG* and discuss the dependence of SFH on stellar mass and environment of the galaxy. We also discuss possible physical motivators to describe our findings.

3.4.1 Star Formation Histories and Environment

To study the effect of environment on the star formation of galaxies we compare the SFH of proto-cluster and field galaxies at $z \sim 2$. Figure 3.4 and 3.6 shows the star formation histories of galaxies in proto-cluster and field environment from ZFIRE -ZFOURGE observations and the *IllustrisTNG* simulations.

Figure 3.4: Specific star formation rate ($\log(\text{SFR}(t)/M_*(t_0))$) histories from ZFIRE - ZFOURGE observations derived with PROSPECTOR vs age of the universe (bottom x-axis) and corresponding redshift (top x-axis) for field (blue) and proto-cluster (red) galaxies at $z \sim 2$. The four panels correspond to 4 mass bins (from left to right): $9 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 9.5$, $9.5 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 10$, $10 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 10.5$, $\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$. The solid and dashed lines show the bootstrapped median sSFH and the shaded region shows the error in median. The number of galaxies in each bin is given in parenthesis in each label. The bottom right panel ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$) shows evidence for the suppressed star formation activity in massive proto-cluster galaxies in the recent time bins.

Figure 3.5: Normalised cumulative stellar mass in galaxies from ZFIRE - ZFOURGE observations derived with PROSPECTOR vs age of the universe (bottom x-axis) and corresponding redshift (top x-axis) for field (blue) and proto-cluster (red) galaxies at $z \sim 2$. The four panels correspond to 4 mass bins (from left to right): $9 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 9.5$, $9.5 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 10$, $10 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 10.5$, $\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$. The solid and dashed lines show the bootstrapped median growth of stellar mass and the shaded region shows the 1σ error in median. The number of galaxies in each bin is given in parenthesis in each label. The bottom right panel ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$) shows evidence of early stellar mass buildup in massive proto-cluster galaxies compared to field galaxies.

Figure 3.6: Instantaneous specific star formation rate ($\log[\text{SFR}(t)/M_{*,z=2}]$) histories from IllustrisTNG vs age of the universe (bottom x-axis) and corresponding redshift (top x-axis) for field (teal) and cluster (orange) galaxies at $z \sim 2$. The four panels are the 4 mass bins (from left to right): $9 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 9.5$, $9.5 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 10$, $10 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 10.5$, $\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$. The solid and dashed lines show the bootstrapped median sSFH and the shaded region shows error in the median. The black dashed lines correspond to the age bins used in SFHs from observations (Figure 3.4). The number of galaxies in each bin is given in parenthesis in each label. Similar to observations, galaxies in the stellar mass bin $10.5 \leq \log(M_*/M_\odot) \leq 11$ (bottom right panel) show effect of environment on the sSFH in contrast to lower mass bins where field and cluster galaxies have comparable sSFH.

3.4.1.1 SFH Vs Environment: Observations

We derive the star formation histories of galaxies at $z \sim 2$ using the extensive **ZFOURGE** photometry and the SED fitting tool **PROSPECTOR**. Figure 3.4 shows the median star formation rates in each age bin normalised to the total stellar mass of the galaxy at the $z \sim 2$ of proto-cluster (red) and field (blue) galaxies. The effect of environment is most evident on the highest mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$). The same trend is not observed in the other mass bins although cluster galaxies in the $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 10 - 10.5$ bin also show slightly ($\sim 1\sigma$) higher star formation in the most recent age bin compared to the field sample ($\log \text{sSFR} = -0.81 \pm 0.09 \text{ Gyr}^{-1}$ in proto-cluster and $-0.92 \pm 0.06 \text{ Gyr}^{-1}$ in field). The different shapes of SFHs across the sample sets also highlight the advantage of using non-parametric SFH vs parametric SFHs.

Massive proto-cluster galaxies show higher star formation in the earliest age bin ($> 1 \text{ Gyr}$ in look-back time; until $\sim 2.1 \text{ Gyr}$ of age of the universe) compared to field sample ($\log \text{sSFR} = -0.65 \pm 0.06 \text{ Gyr}^{-1}$ in proto-cluster and $-0.8 \pm 0.04 \text{ Gyr}^{-1}$ in field) and a lower star formation ($\log \text{sSFR} = -0.71 \pm 0.03 \text{ Gyr}^{-1}$ in proto-cluster and $-0.61 \pm 0.02 \text{ Gyr}^{-1}$ in field) in the more recent age bins ($0 - 200 \text{ Myr}$ in look-back time; $\sim 3.1 - 2.9 \text{ Gyr}$ of age of the universe). This indicates an earlier formation and stellar mass build up of massive proto-cluster galaxies compared to field galaxies.

Figure 3.5 shows the normalised cumulative median stellar mass build-up in proto-cluster (red) and field (blue) galaxies in the four stellar mass bins. The most massive ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) proto-cluster galaxies build up their stellar mass faster than the field galaxies, whereas proto-cluster and field galaxies with $\log(M_*/M_\odot) < 10.5$ have consistent stellar mass build-up history.

Environmental effects arising from the interactions of galaxies with the ICM through processes like ram pressure stripping, starvation, harassment etc. are shown to be more effective in quenching lower mass galaxies, which are rarely quenched in field environment (Medling et al., 2018). In our sample, we do not see any effect of environment on the low mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9 - 9.5$). In the second stellar mass bin ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.5 - 10$), we find a higher SFR in the the most recent age bin (3.1- 3.3 Gyrs in the age of the universe) for proto-cluster galaxies than the field sample. Figure 3.5 shows the difference in the stellar mass formed in the proto-cluster galaxies in the small time scale (200 Myrs) of the most recent age bin is not significant to be seen as a deviation from the

otherwise closely following SFH of the field galaxies. The star formation histories of star forming proto-cluster galaxies in the low mass bins closely follow that of the field galaxies in the same mass bin. Importantly, however, this could be due to the bias of ZFIRE sample towards star forming galaxies of $\text{SFR} > 0.8 \text{ M}_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ (Yuan et al., 2014).

3.4.1.2 SFH Vs Environment: Simulations

The star formation histories from `IllustrisTNG` (Figure 3.6) track the evolution of instantaneous star formation of galaxy in twice the stellar half mass radius of the galaxy in cluster (orange) and field (teal) environment at $z = 2$. The instantaneous SFRs are different from the SFHs based on stellar ages from `PROSPECTOR`, but can still be compared qualitatively. As the observational limit on $\text{H}\alpha$ flux biases our observational sample towards galaxies with $\text{SFR} > 0.8 \text{ M}_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$, we have imposed an analog SFR threshold to the simulated galaxies to have a comparable sample. In practice, we have imposed a SFR cut of $0.4 \text{ M}_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ on the selection of galaxies from `IllustrisTNG` to match the observations (refer to Section 3.3.3).

Figure 3.6 shows the star formation rate normalised to the stellar mass of cluster and field galaxies at $z = 2$ from `IllustrisTNG`. Similar to observations, star formation in cluster galaxies declines with time in the high mass ($\log(\text{M}_{\star}/\text{M}_{\odot}) > 10.5$) sample, whereas in the low mass sample, field and cluster galaxies have comparable SFHs. We also see a slight elevation (< 0.2 dex) of star formation in cluster galaxies compared to field galaxies in mass bin $\log(\text{M}_{\star}/\text{M}_{\odot}) = 10 - 10.5$. The average SFH of low mass galaxies ($\log(\text{M}_{\star}/\text{M}_{\odot}) < 10.5$) is comparable in cluster and field environments.

Contrary to our result of rising of star formation in low mass cluster galaxies, Donnari et al. (2021) find a quenched fraction of ~ 0.4 in the low mass ($9 > \log(\text{M}_{\star}/\text{M}_{\odot}) > 9.5$) satellite galaxies in `IllustrisTNG` at $z = 2$. By selecting galaxies above $\text{SFR} > 0.8 \text{ M}_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ in observations and $> 0.4 \text{ M}_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ in simulations, we are probably removing galaxies whose star formation activity has already been suppressed. This is certainly the case for the simulated sample. For galaxies in the real universe, we can only say that either the star formation in low mass galaxies is not affected by the environment, or that the environmental suppression of star formation happens rapidly in low mass cluster galaxies compared to high mass galaxies.

3.4.2 Star Formation Histories and Stellar Mass

The star formation activity in a galaxy is closely related to its stellar mass at $z = 0 - 4$ (Koyama et al., 2013; Noeske et al., 2007; Tomczak et al., 2016). Since, SFH tracks how galaxies grow its stellar mass, the SFH of galaxies are also related to its stellar mass (Thomas et al., 2005). We find comparable results from the star formation histories derived from ZFOURGE photometry using PROSPECTOR and IllustrisTNG.

3.4.2.1 SFH Vs Stellar Mass: Observations

Figure 3.7 shows dependence of star formation rates in each age bin normalised to the stellar mass of the galaxy at the time of observation. From top left to bottom right, the age bins range from recent to earliest. The most massive galaxies ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) > 10.5$) have higher sSFR (~ 0.6 dex) compared to low mass galaxies in the earliest age bin, indicating that massive galaxies formed their stellar masses early on irrespective of the environment. Compared to that, towards the most recent age bin ($0 - 200$ Myr), we find this trend gradually reverses. In the most recent age bin ($0 - 200$ Myr, the most massive galaxies have lower sSFR (~ 0.8 dex) compared to the lowest mass galaxies.

From SED fitting of observations with PROSPECTOR, figure 3.5 shows that the high mass cluster galaxies ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) > 10.5$) form $\approx 45 \pm 8\%$ of stellar mass in the first ~ 2 Gyr of the universe compared to $9 \pm 1\%$ to $19 \pm 2\%$ of stars formed for lower stellar mass galaxies in the same environment. In the field sample, the high mass galaxies ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) > 10.5$) form $\approx 31 \pm 2\%$ of their stellar mass in the first ~ 2 Gyr of the universe compared to $12 \pm 1\%$ to $17 \pm 1\%$ in the lower stellar mass galaxies. Figure 3.4 also shows that the shape of the SFH for galaxies is dependent on the stellar mass of the galaxies. The highest mass bin have a constant SFH compared to galaxies in the lowest mass bin, for which the median SFH is rising. Whereas galaxies in stellar mass range $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 9.5 - 10.5$ have a bursty star formation history.

The rising SFH is measured only in the lowest stellar mass galaxies, where the observational limitation of our sample excludes low stellar mass galaxies with low star formation rates. The low stellar mass galaxies that have suppressed star formation either due to environmental or secular processes are thus not included in our sample and this would explain the rising SFH measured in the lowest stellar mass bin for our sample.

Figure 3.7: Specific Star formation rate ($\text{SFR}(t)/M_{*z=2}$) from observations vs stellar mass in 5 look back time age bins: 0 – 200 Myr, 200 – 400 Myr, 400 – 600 Myr, 600 – 1000 Myr and > 1 Gyr (top-left to bottom right) for proto-cluster (red circles) and field (blue diamonds) galaxies. The sSFRs are plotted against the median stellar mass of each mas bin. The error bars represent the error in median. In the earliest age bin ($t = 1-2$ Gyr) massive galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_{\odot}) = 10 - 11$) are forming more stars compared to lower stellar mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_{\odot}) = 9 - 10$) in contrast to the most recent age bin ($t = 0-200$ Myr), where lower mass galaxies are forming more stars than the massive galaxies across environments.

3.4.2.2 SFH Vs Stellar Mass: Simulations

Figure 3.6 shows the star formation rates of the cluster and field galaxies from `IllustrisTNG`. The SFHs of TNG100 galaxies show similar trends to the observations. The SFH of high stellar mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10$) either plateaus with time in the field environment or drops in clusters. On the other hand, low stellar mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) < 10$) have rising SFHs irrespective of the environment. This result is comparable to our observations (Figure 3.4). The SFH of galaxies from `IllustrisTNG` in the highest stellar mass bin ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) plateaus ≈ 500 Myr earlier than the galaxies in mass bin ($10 > \log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) and ≈ 1 Gyr earlier than the galaxies in mass bin ($9.5 > \log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10$). Massive galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) form most stars ($38 \pm 3\%$ and $32 \pm 0.4\%$ of their total stellar mass in proto-cluster and field environments, respectively) in the first 2 Gyr.

Our analysis indicates an earlier formation and evolution of massive galaxies irrespective of environment compared to lower mass galaxies. This result is in agreement to many theoretical and observational studies (Renzini, 2016; Sánchez-Blázquez et al., 2006; Thomas et al., 2005). Recent observational study by Webb et al. (2020) have comparable results for quenched galaxies at $z < 1.5$. Thomas et al. (2005) show that most massive early type galaxies at $z = 0$ have peak star formation activity 1 – 2 Gyr before low stellar mass galaxies, comparable to our results.

3.4.3 Stellar Age: Mass and Environment

Our results from `ZFOURGE` and `IllustrisTNG` show significant effect of environment on the SFH of high mass galaxies at $z = 2$. In this Section, we explore in `IllustrisTNG` if earlier formation or merger histories could explain the measured decline in star formation activity of massive cluster galaxies.

To estimate if massive galaxies in the proto-cluster environment formed earlier than the field galaxies, we analyse the average age of their stellar populations in `IllustrisTNG`. We extract the mass weighted stellar age for each galaxy in our field and cluster environment as follows:

$$t_g = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N t_i M_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N M_i} \quad (3.1)$$

where t_g is the mass weighted stellar age of the galaxy, t_i and M_i are the age and mass of each stellar particle in the galaxy and N is the total number of stellar particles in the galaxy. We use the snapshot particle data of *IllustrisTNG* (Nelson et al., 2019) to get the stellar ages of galaxies at $z = 2$. Figure 3.8 shows the mass weighted stellar ages of the cluster (orange) and field (teal) galaxies in the respective stellar mass bins. The error bars show the error in the median of the distribution.

Figure 3.8: Mass weighted stellar age (Gyr) vs log stellar mass (M_{\odot}) of the galaxy in cluster (orange) and field (teal) environments at $z = 2$ in *IllustrisTNG*. The massive galaxies ($\log(M_{*}/M_{\odot}) > 10.5$) are ≈ 190 Myr older than the low mass galaxies ($\log(M_{*}/M_{\odot}) = 9 - 9.5$). Stellar population in cluster galaxies have comparable ages to the field galaxies across the stellar mass range.

The median mass weighted stellar ages increase with the stellar mass of the galaxy in the cluster. The mass-weighted stellar ages of cluster galaxies is comparable to those of the field galaxies across the stellar mass ages. Our results do not change significantly when comparing the ages of the oldest stellar particle in the galaxy.

The median stellar ages of the lowest mass galaxies ($\log(M_{*}/M_{\odot}) = 9 - 9.5$) is $\approx 800 \pm 20$ Myr and high mass galaxies ($\log(M_{*}/M_{\odot}) > 10.5$) is $\approx 980 \pm 10$ Gyr. The highest mass galaxies are $\approx 190 \pm 30$ Myr older than the low stellar mass galaxies. The cluster galaxies

are the same age as the field galaxies across the stellar mass bin. This result is different to the observational study by Webb et al. (2020), who find that at $z = 1$, cluster galaxies are 310 Myr older than the field galaxies in the mass bin $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 10 - 11.8$.

3.4.4 Merger events

Many theoretical and observational studies correlate galaxy mergers with stellar mass growth, increased gas fractions, enhanced AGN activity and enhanced SFR (Dutta et al., 2018; Ellison et al., 2015; Hani et al., 2020; Kewley et al., 2006; Moreno et al., 2019). Watson et al. (2019) show that galaxy mergers are twice as frequent in the proto-cluster environment compared to the field at $z \sim 2$. Using `IllustrisTNG` Hani et al. (2020) show that the enhancement of the SFR activity due to mergers correlates with the stellar mass, mass ratio and the gas fraction of the merging pair. The decay of SFR enhancement in post merger phase happens over 500 Myr and the galaxies that underwent strongest merger driven starburst events quench on a faster timescale.

We explore if the differences in the SFH of massive galaxies between environments is driven by mergers. We use the merger catalogs by Rodriguez-Gomez et al. (2015) from `IllustrisTNG` to explore the effect of merger on the star formation histories. Figure 3.9 shows that the distribution of total mergers (mass ratio > 0.1) encountered in cluster (orange) and field (teal) environment in different stellar mass bins is comparable. However, massive galaxies ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) > 10.5$) on average have experienced 8 ± 0.3 and 10 ± 1 mergers (mass ratio > 0.1) in field and cluster sample respectively, compared to 5 ± 0.3 mergers experienced by low mass cluster and field galaxies ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 9 - 9.5$) in their lifetimes.

While merger events often lead to further star formation, gas poor mergers do not and in turn will not affect the average stellar age of the galaxy. To estimate if massive galaxies have experienced gas poor mergers we analyse the cold gas fraction and total gas fraction of the mergers. We use the merger history catalogs by Rodriguez-Gomez et al. (2017) to get the mean cold gas fraction (weighted by the stellar mass) of all the progenitors until $z = 2$ (Figure 3.10). The mean cold gas fraction of cluster and field galaxies are comparable across stellar mass bins.

To calculate if the difference in SFHs could be driven by the total supply of gas, we

Figure 3.9: Distribution of total number of mergers (mass ratio > 0.1) in field (teal) and cluster (orange) galaxies in four stellar mass bins in *IllustrisTNG* at $z = 2$. (left to right: $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9-9.5$, $9.5-10$, $10-10.5$, ≥ 10.5). Massive galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) on average have experienced 3-5 more mergers (mass ratio > 0.1) compared to the low mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9-9.5$) in both cluster and field environment.

calculate the total gas fraction of the progenitors for galaxies at each redshift snapshot as:

$$f_{gas,z} = \frac{\sum_{p=1}^N M_{gas,p,z}}{\sum_{p=1}^N M_{gas,p,z} + \sum_{p=1}^N M_{*,p,z}} \quad (3.2)$$

where $f_{gas,z}$ is the total gas fraction of all progenitors (p) at redshift z , $M_{gas,p,z}$ and $M_{*,p,z}$ are the total gas mass and stellar mass of each progenitor p at the same redshift snapshot z .

Figure 3.10: Mean cold gas fraction in mergers Vs stellar mass of galaxies in field (teal diamonds) and cluster (orange circles) environment. The markers show the median and error bars are error in median for the sample. The mean cold gas fraction of mergers decreases with increasing stellar mass of the galaxies and are comparable across environments.

Figure 3.11 shows the total gas fraction of the progenitors for the cluster (orange) and field (teal) galaxies in the 4 stellar mass bins. The cluster galaxies in the highest stellar mass bin ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) encounter lower gas fractions mergers consistently since 1 Gyr after the Big Bang compared to field galaxies in the same stellar mass bin. On the other hand, the total gas fraction of progenitors in the lower stellar mass bin ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9 - 9.5$) are comparable across environments throughout their merger histories.

3.5 Discussion

The star formation rate of a galaxy depends strongly on its stellar mass and local environment. This dependence has been demonstrated to evolve since $z \sim 2$ in both observations and cosmological simulations (Darvish et al., 2017; Donnari et al., 2020, 2019, 2021; Kawinwanichakij et al., 2017a; Muzzin et al., 2012; Peng et al., 2010; Tomczak et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015; Webb et al., 2020). In this work, we have compared the star formation histories of star-forming galaxies in the cluster and field environments at $z \sim 2$ using observations and simulations.

3.5.1 Star Formation History: Environment and Stellar Mass

In Section 4.4 we have shown that the star formation histories of galaxies from ZFOURGE at $z \sim 2$ strongly depends on the stellar mass of the galaxy in both proto-cluster and field environments. Figure 3.5 shows that galaxies in the highest mass bin have formed $45 \pm 8\%$ and $31 \pm 2\%$ (in proto-cluster and field environments) of their present stellar mass in the first ~ 2 Gyr. Compared to the high mass galaxies in the same time epoch (first ~ 2 Gyr), the lowest mass galaxies form $< 20\%$ of their present stellar mass in both proto-cluster and field environments. The star formation histories from PROSPECTOR also show that the most massive galaxies have a constant or declining star formation history as opposed to the rising star formation history of the lowest mass galaxies in both high and low density environments. This points to a faster and early stellar mass build up in the most massive galaxies and a delayed evolution of the lowest mass galaxies.

This result is consistent with the observational and theoretical studies that show a mass dependence of star formation histories (Poggianti et al., 2006; Thomas et al., 2005, 2010; Webb et al., 2020). These studies show that the evolution of more massive galaxies happen over shorter time scales compared to their lower mass counterparts. Stellar population studies predict a difference of ~ 2 Gyr between the evolution of high mass cluster early type galaxies and high mass field early type galaxies at $z \sim 0$ (Renzini, 2006; Thomas et al., 2005), which is over estimated compared to our results. However, the 2 Gyr difference could be a result of redshift evolution.

In our sample, the effect of environment on SFH of star forming galaxies in $z \sim 2$ proto-cluster is present only in the highest mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$). The massive

Figure 3.11: Total gas fraction of progenitors Vs age of the universe for four stellar mass bins in field and cluster environment. Progenitors of the most massive cluster galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$, solid orange line) are consistently gas poorer in comparison to the progenitors of field galaxies in the same stellar mass bin (teal solid line) since ~ 1 Gyr of the age of the universe.

proto-cluster galaxies, which form $\approx 45 \pm 8\%$ of their stellar mass in the first 2 Gyr, have a declining star formation history compared to the massive field galaxies which forms $\approx 31 \pm 2\%$ of their stellar mass in the first ≈ 2 Gyr (Figure 3.5). The field galaxies takes ≈ 2.8 Gyr to form 46% of its total stellar mass. This shows a slower and delayed (by 0.8 Gyr) evolution of high mass field galaxies compared to the proto-cluster galaxies. The lack of environmental effect on the SFH of low mass galaxies at $z \sim 2$ is comparable to the result in Papovich et al. (2018), who find that the environmental quenching efficiency of galaxies decreases with stellar mass until $z \sim 0.5$. Our conclusion for the observed low mass galaxies remains to be confirmed with an observational sample with SFR completeness below SFR threshold of $0.8 M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$.

We find similar trends of star formation histories in consistently-selected galaxies from IllustrisTNG (Figure 3.6). As we go from the highest mass galaxies to the lowest mass galaxies we see that the plateauing of star formation occurs earlier for high mass galaxies

compared to the low mass sample. For the highest mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 10.5 - 11$) the star formation plateaus at ~ 1.5 Gyr compared to ~ 2 Gyr, and 2.7 Gyr for galaxies in $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 10 - 10.5$ and $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.5 - 10$ mass bins respectively. Galaxies in the lowest mass bin ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9 - 9.5$) have a rising star formation until $z = 2$. This also indicates early evolution of massive galaxies comparable to our results from PROSPECTOR. We also find that the environment significantly affects the star formation histories of galaxies in the highest mass bin, with cluster galaxies forming more stars early on compared to the field galaxies similar to our results from observations.

In *IllustrisTNG*, the stellar mass formed by the most massive galaxies in the first 2 Gyr of the universe is $38 \pm 3\%$ in the cluster and $32 \pm 0.4\%$ in the field. The difference in fraction of stellar mass formed in the first 2 Gyr of the universe is within 1σ error ($6 \pm 3.4\%$) compared to the observations ($14 \pm 10\%$). Cluster and field galaxies in the lowest mass bin form $24 \pm 0.7\%$ and $23 \pm 0.5\%$ of their total stellar mass at $z = 2$ which is lower than the fraction of total stellar mass formed in high mass galaxies, similar to our results from observations.

In *IllustrisTNG*, Donnari et al. (2020) show that the fraction of quenched satellite galaxies at $z = 2$ is $\sim 0.2 - 0.4$ in the stellar mass range $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9 - 9.5$ and $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 10.5 - 11$. Due to the SFR cut imposed on the selection of galaxies from *IllustrisTNG* to match the observations, we do not see the suppression of SFH in low mass cluster galaxies. The low mass cluster galaxies experiencing the effect of environment and undergoing suppression of star formation would thus be removed due to the SFR threshold. We need spectroscopic redshift confirmation of faint ($K_{AB} > 24$) galaxies at $z \sim 2$ to be able to measure the effect of environment on SFH of the low mass quenched galaxies.

3.5.2 Early Formation?

Our results from the observations (ZFIRE - ZFOURGE) and *IllustrisTNG* simulations show signs of the onset of the star formation quenching in the most massive galaxies in the cluster environment. Using the *IllustrisTNG* simulations, we investigate a possible earlier formation of cluster galaxies driving the difference in SFHs (3.4.1 and 3.4.2). Galaxies in

the most massive bin are $\approx 190 \pm 30$ Myr older than lowest mass galaxies. Our result is unaffected if we consider the age of oldest stellar particle in the galaxy age as a proxy for formation time instead of the mass weighted stellar ages.

The age difference of $\approx 190 \pm 30$ Myr at $z = 2$ between high and low stellar mass galaxies is consistent with the observational results at redshift $z \sim 1$ where cluster galaxies are $\sim 300 - 400$ Myr older than the field galaxies (van Dokkum & van der Marel, 2007; Webb et al., 2020) and ~ 1 Gyr at $z \sim 0.1$ (Thomas et al., 2005). The increasing difference in stellar ages could be driven by the redshift evolution of ages of cluster and field galaxies. Nevertheless, the mass weighted stellar ages are unable to explain the measured difference in SFH of massive galaxies in cluster and field in our sample. This indicates that the suppression of star formation in high stellar mass cluster galaxies at $z = 2$ in *IllustrisTNG* is not a result of earlier formation and evolution.

3.5.3 Role of Mergers

Studies have shown that massive galaxies grow their stellar mass through mergers (Gupta et al., 2020; Pillepich et al., 2018a; Rodriguez-Gomez et al., 2015). Recent work by Hani et al. (2020) uses *IllustrisTNG* to find that mergers enhance the SFR of post merger galaxies, but the relative increase in SFR depends on the stellar mass, mass ratio of the progenitor pair and the gas fraction of the progenitors. We investigate the possible role of mergers in shaping the SFHs.

We track the merger histories (mass ratio > 0.1) of our sample from *IllustrisTNG* and find that in the combined cluster+field sample, on average massive galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$) experience 8 ± 0.26 mergers compared to 5 ± 0.03 mergers encountered by the low mass galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9 - 9.5$) in $2 \leq z < 20$ (Figure 3.9). We speculate that the higher number of mergers experienced by massive galaxies early on leads to the build up of stellar mass and higher SFR in the earlier time bins. The higher SFRs of massive galaxies in the early time bins (Figures 3.4, 3.6) could lead to the depletion of gas reservoir faster compared to the lower mass galaxies (Figure 3.11). The decreasing mean cold gas fraction of mergers with stellar mass of the galaxy also indicates the depletion of star formation fuel in the massive galaxies compared to the low stellar mass galaxies, explaining the relatively flat SFHs of massive galaxies (Figure 3.7).

The effect of environment on the SFHs of galaxies is only evident in the highest mass bin ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$) in both observations (Figure 3.4) and simulations (Figure 3.6). The high mass cluster galaxies experience more mergers (10 ± 1) compared to the high mass field galaxies (8 ± 0.3 mergers). Moreover, the progenitors of the massive cluster galaxies at $z = 2$ have lower total gas fraction than the progenitors of high mass field galaxies even when the universe was 1 Gyr old (Figure 3.11). Although, the mean cold gas fraction of the progenitors of two population is comparable at $z = 2$ (Figure 3.10).

We hypothesize that the observed suppression of sSFR in massive cluster galaxies in the recent time bins is a delayed effect of the lower gas fraction in its progenitors. In other words, we find that massive galaxies in proto-clusters at $z \sim 2$ show signatures of environmental effects not because of direct environmental processes due to their interaction with other cluster galaxies or the intra-halo medium, but rather because of the very nature of the environment they live in, which in turn affects their merger history and their opportunities to acquire gas.

Star formation rapidly progresses in the massive cluster galaxies with the available gas reservoirs. However, by $z = 2$ massive cluster galaxies are starved because recent mergers have been systematically gas poorer in comparison to the massive field galaxies. The early onset of depletion of the gas reservoir in the massive cluster galaxies would cause the suppression of star formation by $z = 2$ and could lead to an eventual quenching in the future via starvation. The environment-dependent depletion of gas fractions progresses from massive to low mass galaxies as we approach $z = 2$ (Figure 3.11). This suggests that the massive cluster galaxies would grow via dry mergers in the low redshift universe (Tran et al., 2005; Webb et al., 2015), and the environmental quenching would progress from massive galaxies to low mass galaxies in the cluster environment as is observed in the low redshift universe (Donnari et al., 2021).

In a recent work (Gupta et al., 2021) find that in *IllustrisTNG* star formation quenching in massive galaxies depends on their stellar size and is driven by the black hole feedback (Davies et al., 2020; Zinger et al., 2020). In future, we will test if the signs of early onset of star formation suppression in massive cluster galaxies is imprinted on the size of their stellar disks. We will further investigate if the growth and feedback of central super massive black hole is affected by the local environment of the galaxy.

3.6 Summary

In this work, we have presented the first measurements of the SFHs of galaxies in the proto-cluster environment at $z = 2$ using the ZFIRE - ZFOURGE surveys. We have compared our results with the SFHs of galaxies in different environments in the IllustrisTNG simulations and used the latter to provide a possible physical interpretation of the our findings. Our main results are summarised as:

1. **ZFIRE - ZFOURGE:** The SFHs of massive star forming galaxies ($10.5 \leq \log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) \leq 11$) in the proto-cluster are constant compared to the field galaxies in the same mass bin (Figure 3.4). In the first two Gyr of age of the universe, massive proto-cluster galaxies form $45 \pm 8\%$ of total stellar mass compared to $31 \pm 2\%$ formed in massive field galaxies (Figure 3.5). However, a similar dependence of SFHs on environment is not observed in galaxies in the lower mass bin ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) \leq 10.5$).
2. **ZFIRE - ZFOURGE:** High mass galaxies form more stars (45 ± 8 to $31 \pm 2\%$ in cluster and field environment respectively) in the earliest age bin (> 2 Gyr age of universe), compared to low stellar mass galaxies ($17 \pm 1\%$ to $19 \pm 2\%$ in cluster and field environment respectively) in the same age bin (Figure 3.5). This indicates a faster/earlier stellar mass build up of massive galaxies.
3. **IllustrisTNG:** SFHs from simulations are comparable to our results from observations. The effect of environment is most prominent in the most massive galaxies (Figure 3.6). Star formation in most massive cluster galaxies is suppressed compared to the field galaxies in the same mass bin. However, the SFHs of low mass galaxies do not show any dependence on environment.
4. **Stellar Ages:** In IllustrisTNG, low mass galaxies are on average 190 Myr younger than the high mass galaxies. However there is no difference in stellar ages in different environments across the studied stellar mass range (Figure 3.8). Hence, the observed differences in the SFHs between cluster and field massive galaxies cannot be a result of early formation or earlier evolution of massive cluster galaxies.
5. **Mergers and Gas Fractions:** Based on the outcome of IllustrisTNG, we find that massive galaxies on average have experienced more mergers than low mass galaxies (5 mergers), irrespective of their environment (Figure 3.9) by $z = 2$. The mean cold fractions

in mergers decrease with increasing stellar mass but are comparable across environments (Figure 3.10). On the other hand, the total gas fractions in the progenitors of massive cluster galaxies are consistently lower since ~ 1 Gyr after the Big Bang in comparison to field massive galaxies (Figure 3.11).

We hence hypothesize that the reduced star formation in the massive cluster galaxies at $z \sim 2$ is a delayed cumulative effect of the lower gas fractions in their progenitors due to the very environment they evolve in instead of direct interactions with other cluster galaxies or the intra-cluster medium.

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Chapter 4

The Gas Inflow Inequality for Satellite Galaxies in Cluster and Field Halos at $z = 2$.

4.1 Abstract

The history of gas inflow into galaxies should affect the star formation and hence the evolution of galaxies across cosmic time. In this work, we use `IllustrisTNG` to understand the role of environment on gas inflow rates in galaxies at $z \geq 2$. We divide our galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 10.5$) into centrals and satellites in cluster ($\log M_{\text{halo}}/M_\odot \geq 13$) and field ($\log M_{\text{halo}}/M_\odot < 13$) halos at $z = 2$ and track their gas inflow rates from $z = 6$ to 2. We find that the total gas inflow rates of satellite galaxies rapidly decline after their infall into cluster halos and as they reach the cluster center. At $z = 2$, the gas inflow rate of cluster satellite galaxies is correlated with the cluster-centric radii and not the host halo mass. In contrast, the gas inflow rate in centrals is strongly correlated with the host halo mass at $z \geq 2$. Our study indicates that between $z = 6$ to 2, the gas that normally is accreted by the satellite galaxies is redirected to the center of the cluster halo as inflows to the cluster centrals and forming the intra-cluster medium. The inequality of gas accretion between massive satellite and central galaxies is responsible for the starvation of cluster satellite galaxies that evolve into the massive quenched cluster galaxies observed at $z < 0.5$.

4.2 Introduction

Understanding gas flows is quintessential to understanding the evolution of star formation in a galaxy and hence galaxy growth. In the Λ CDM model of the universe, pristine metal-poor gas is accreted onto galaxies as fuel for star formation over cosmic time. As star formation progresses, the gas reservoir of the galaxy is depleted and energetically ejected in form of winds and outflows driven by star formation or the active-galactic nuclei (AGN). The ejected gas is metal-enriched and may either be accreted back onto the galaxy or enrich the circum-galactic medium (CGM) and the inter-galactic medium (IGM). The progression of the baryonic cycle across cosmic time describes the properties of galaxies, and yet remains poorly understood.

Numerical simulations predict that gas accretion in a galaxy can proceed in several ways. Gas accreted onto a massive galaxy ($\log M_h/M_\odot > 11$) from the surrounding IGM is shock heated and will eventually radiatively cool (Rees & Ostriker, 1977; Silk, 1977) and settle onto the galactic disk. This is called "hot-mode" accretion. Alternatively, pristine gas can flow into the galaxy via filaments from the cosmic web or satellite galaxies and is called "cold-mode" accretion (Kereš et al., 2009, 2005; Nelson et al., 2013; Stern et al., 2019; Wright et al., 2021). Galaxies can also acquire gas from mergers with other galaxies. The different modes of gas accretion occur simultaneously and leave different imprints on the evolution of galaxies and their star formation.

The environment of a galaxy has been shown to correlate with star formation rates and interstellar medium properties of galaxies as early as $z = 2$ (Alcorn et al., 2019; Gupta et al., 2018; Harshan et al., 2021, 2020; Kawinwanichakij et al., 2017b; Scoville et al., 2013; Tran et al., 2010). Gravitational and hydrodynamical interactions with other galaxies and the intra-cluster medium (ICM) in dense environments preferentially affects the gas in satellite galaxies (Cortese et al., 2021; Fumagalli et al., 2009; Gunn & Gott $_{III}$, 1972; Moore et al., 1996). At lower redshifts $z < 0.8$, studies find a deficiency of atomic and molecular gas fractions in galaxies in high density environments (Brown et al., 2017; Peng et al., 2015; Scott et al., 2012). In contrast, studies of galaxies in proto-clusters at $z > 1.5$ find higher gas fractions (Aoyama et al., 2022; Hayashi et al., 2017; Noble et al., 2017; Rudnick et al., 2017). However, measuring gas fractions in galaxies at $z > 1$ remains challenging due to sensitivity limits and access to key spectral lines.

Environment plays a crucial role in regulating the gas accretion history of individual

galaxies. Numerical simulations suggest that galaxies residing in the filaments of the cosmic web acquire their gas mass through cold-mode accretion (Birnboim & Dekel, 2003; Kereš et al., 2009; Liao & Gao, 2019; Ocvirk et al., 2008). Using cosmological simulations, studies like Simha et al. (2009) and van de Voort et al. (2017a) find that satellite galaxies in massive halos have lower gas accretion compared to central galaxies. van de Voort et al. (2017a) also find that the gas inflow rate in central galaxies is not strongly affected by the environment of the galaxy. In a recent study, Chun et al. (2020) show that at $z < 5$, when the gas in the cosmic web is ionized, accretion of gas is a function of surrounding gas density and the position/proximity of the galaxy to the cosmic web. On the other hand, galaxies that fall into massive halos lose their gas reservoir due to interaction with the cluster potential, the ICM, or nearby galaxies.

Observational studies of gas inflows remain challenging at higher redshifts and have relied on the detection of Ly α emission around quasars and protoclusters, or quasar sightlines (Daddi et al., 2021, 2022; Dijkstra & Loeb, 2009; Fu et al., 2021; Umehata et al., 2019; Zabl et al., 2019). Additionally, interpretation of the observational results of inflows is made complicated by the effect of outflows, active galactic nuclei (AGN), and star formation. Studies using Ly α emission line find a higher occurrence of Ly α emitting halos around high density environments at $z > 2$ indicating active gas accretion (Daddi et al., 2021, 2022; Umehata et al., 2019), however, accretion in isolated galaxies in the high redshift universe is not easily observable.

In Harshan et al. (2021), using *IllustrisTNG* we show that the massive galaxies in the proto-cluster environment at $z \sim 2$ have been gas poor since $z \sim 5$ compared to their field counterparts. We hypothesize that lower gas fractions in massive proto-cluster galaxies directly result in lower star formation in cluster environment as measured using the star formation histories from ZFOURGE - ZFIRE observations (Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Straatman et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015). The lower gas fraction can arise due to a lower inflow of gas from the surrounding medium either due to feedback, (Zinger et al., 2020) or the position of the galaxy in the cosmic web, gas poor mergers, and outflows. In this chapter, we test our hypothesis by tracking how gas inflow onto individual galaxies varies with the environment.

This chapter is organized as follows. In section 4.3, we describe the data from cosmological simulations *IllustrisTNG* and methodology to describe gas inflows. In sections 4.4 and 4.5 we state our results and discussion, and in section 4.6 summarise the results. For this work,

we assume a flat Λ CDM cosmology with $\Omega_M = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, and $H_0 = 69.6 \text{ kms}^{-1}\text{Mpc}^{-1}$.

4.3 IllustrisTNG and Methodology

IllustrisTNG is a suite of magneto-hydro-dynamical cosmological simulations based on the Λ CDM cosmology (Marinacci et al., 2018; Naiman et al., 2018; Nelson et al., 2018; Pillepich et al., 2018a; Springel et al., 2018). **IllustrisTNG** extends the Illustris framework with kinetic black hole feedback, magneto-hydrodynamics, and a revised scheme for galactic winds, among other changes (Pillepich et al., 2018a; Weinberger et al., 2017). TNG100 spans a range of galaxy environments including halo masses as high as $M_{\text{halo}} \sim 10^{15} M_\odot$ at $z = 0$ making it ideal for this analysis.

In this work, we use the TNG100 box with $L_{\text{box}} = 110.7 \text{ cMpc}$, and a total volume $\sim 10^6 \text{ Mpc}^3$, to map the gas inflow rate histories of the cluster and field galaxies at $z = 2$. The data of TNG100 is publicly available and described by Nelson et al. (2019). The TNG100 simulation has a baryonic mass resolution of $m_b = 1.4 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ which provides about 1000 stellar particles per galaxy for a galaxy with stellar mass $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9$, and proportionally more stellar particles for more massive galaxies.

Following the cluster selection in Harshan et al. (2021) (Chapter 3), we select galaxies associated with halos of $M_{\text{halo}} \geq 10^{13} M_\odot$ as cluster galaxies and galaxies in halos $M_{\text{halo}} < 10^{13} M_\odot$ as field galaxies at $z = 2$. We further divide the cluster and field sample into central and satellite populations. The central galaxy of each halo is defined as the most massive galaxy in the friends-of-friends (FOF) group (halo) and satellite galaxies in each halo are all galaxies except the central in the FOF group (halo).

In Harshan et al. (2021), we find that only the most massive galaxies show a consistently low total gas fraction in the progenitors and hence, for this analysis we are only considering massive galaxies at $\log M_*/M_\odot \geq 10.5$ in both cluster and field halos. To separate the effect of stellar mass and environment, we have mass matched the field sample (both centrals and satellites) with the cluster satellite sample (Table 4.1). Mass matching is done by selecting galaxies in the field sample within ± 0.01 dex range of each cluster satellite galaxy. Ultimately, we get a sample of 394 galaxies in the field centrals, 69 field satellites and 44 cluster satellite galaxies. The central galaxies in cluster halos are significantly more massive than the cluster satellite populations and due to small number sample (24),

we are unable to mass match the cluster central sample to the cluster satellite sample meaningfully (Sample sets are summarised in Table 4.1).

Figure 4.1: The stellar mass distribution of field ($\log M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\odot} < 13$) centrals (solid blue line) and field satellites (dashed yellow line) stellar mass matched with the cluster ($\log M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\odot} \geq 13$) satellites (red dashed line) from *IllustrisTNG* at $z = 2$. The solid teal line shows the stellar mass distribution of the cluster centrals. The dashed vertical lines indicate the median value of each sample indicated by the respective color and the number of galaxies in each sample is indicated in the label.

The stellar mass distribution of four samples is presented in Figure 4.1 with median stellar mass for each sample indicated with vertical dashed lines. The median stellar mass for field centrals ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 10.6 \pm 0.1$), field satellites ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 10.6 \pm 0.1$) and cluster satellites ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 10.6 \pm 0.1$) fall within 1σ deviation. The median stellar mass for the cluster centrals is $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 11.2 \pm 0.2$. We perform the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to test the equality of the mass matched sample (excluding the massive cluster central population). We calculate the K-S test statistic of 0.1 and p-value = 0.73 between the field centrals and cluster satellites and 0.15 (K-S statistic) and 0.50 (p-value) between the

field and cluster satellites. Thus the stellar mass distribution of selected field centrals and satellites conforms to the stellar mass distribution of the cluster satellites. Throughout the chapter, field centrals are referred to as ‘F centrals’, field satellites as ‘F satellites’, cluster centrals are referred to as ‘C centrals’ and cluster satellites as ‘C satellites’ in the figure legends.

Table 4.1: Summary of selected centrals and satellites sample in field and cluster environments.

Sample	Sample Size	$\log(M_*/M_\odot)^a$	Gas Radii ^b	$\log R/R_{200}^c$	$\log D_5^d$
F Satellites	69	10.6 ± 0.1	15.8 ± 0.8	0.9 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.1
F Centrals	394	10.6 ± 0.1	24.5 ± 1.0	-	2.2 ± 0.0
C Satellites	44	10.6 ± 0.1	17.3 ± 1.3	0.5 ± 0.2	1.9 ± 0.0
C Centrals ^e	24	11.2 ± 0.2	27.6 ± 2.4	-	1.6 ± 0.1

^a Median log Stellar Mass of the sample

^b Median Gas Radii is presented in kpc

^c Median Halo-centric Distance (R) normalised by the R_{200} of the host halo

^d Median log of fifth nearest neighbour distance is presented in kpc

^e C Centrals are not stellar mass matched with C Satellites

4.3.1 Measuring Gas Inflows

We measure the gas radii of the galaxies by calculating the cumulative total gas density profile of each galaxy within 10 times the stellar half mass radii, in order to minimize the contribution of gas from the halo itself. The central galaxies in both field and cluster halos do not show a clear flattening in the gas density profiles like the satellite galaxies. Hence, we consider the radii where normalized cumulative gas density reaches 0.9 as the gas radii of the galaxy. The median gas radii of the four samples are reported in Table 4.1. The median gas radii for the entire stellar mass matched sample (i.e., field centrals, field satellites and cluster satellites) is 22.4 ± 0.8 kpc.

At about twice the stellar half-mass radius, the gas is turbulent due to star formation feedback as winds and outflows. Thus, we calculate the inflowing gas at approximately the gas radii. We calculate the inflowing gas at 20 kpc radii in a 5 kpc shell by calculating the radial velocity of each gas cell in the prescribed shell and measure the total gas mass

inflow rate at a specific redshift as:

$$\dot{M}_{\text{in,gas}}(z) = \sum_{i=0}^N v_{\text{rad},i,z} M_{i,z} / \Delta r \quad (4.1)$$

where $v_{\text{rad},i,z}$ is the radial velocity of each gas cell of mass $M_{i,z}$ at radius $20 < r_i < 25$ kpc from the center of the galaxy at each redshift z . The radial velocity is calculated with respect to the center of the galaxy taking into account the motion of the galaxy and the local Hubble expansion. Additionally, we measure the gas inflow rates using gas cells with $v_{\text{rad}} < -50$ km/s in the considered shell. Gas inflow rates calculated at $z = 2, 3, 4$ and 6 are summarised in Table 4.2.

Figure 4.2 shows an example of a central and a satellite galaxy. The top panel shows the column density of total gas with density increasing from purple to yellow. The bottom panel show the radial velocity of the gas cells associated with the galaxy such that the inflowing gas is colored in green and the outflowing gas is red. The images are overlaid with the spherical shell shown in white in which the gas inflow rate is calculated.

We use data from the SUBLINK algorithm which tracks the merger histories of the galaxies (Rodriguez-Gomez et al., 2015) to quantitatively follow the evolution of galaxies and consider only the main progenitor branch (considering the most massive progenitors at each snapshot) to calculate the gas inflow rates and associated histories of the galaxies.

4.4 Results: History of Gas Inflow Rates

We measure the history of total gas inflow rates of satellite and central galaxies in field ($M_{\text{halo}} < 10^{13} M_{\odot}$) and cluster ($M_{\text{halo}} \geq 10^{13} M_{\odot}$) halos at $z \geq 2$ as described in section 4.3.1 and show in Figure 4.3. The stellar mass matched field satellites (Yellow dashed line; Figure 4.3) and field centrals (Blue solid line ; Figure 4.3) have a similar history of gas inflow rates. In contrast, the stellar mass matched cluster satellite galaxies (Red dashed line; Figure 4.3) have higher gas inflow rates compared to the field (centrals + satellites) sample at $z > 4$, after which the gas inflow rates in cluster satellites decrease drastically (≈ 0.5 dex decline) by $z = 2$. The decline in gas inflow rates in cluster satellites indicates an effect of environment in the early universe (at $6 > z > 2$). However, the effect of environment in decreasing the gas inflow rates in satellites is measured in cluster halos only.

4.4. RESULTS: HISTORY OF GAS INFLOW RATES

Figure 4.2: Gas column density (top) and radial velocity (bottom) distribution of gas in two example galaxies at $z = 2$ (left: satellite; right: central) projected face-on. The white shells depict the 20 kpc and 25 kpc radii from the center of the galaxy and the green circle defines the stellar half mass radius. We calculate the rate of inflowing gas in the 5 kpc shell at 20 kpc radii from the center of the galaxy. The inflowing gas is shown in green with darkness increasing with the increasing radial velocity and the outflowing gas is depicted in red. The images are 100 kpc x 100 kpc at $z = 2$ from the IllustrisTNG website.

Cluster centrals (Teal solid line; Figure 4.3) have an increasing gas inflow rate at $6 > z > 3$, after which the gas inflow rate is constant for the next 1.3 Gyrs. By $z = 2$, cluster centrals have a ≈ 0.5 dex higher gas inflow rate compared to the field centrals (Table 4.2). However, cluster centrals are not stellar mass matched with the other three sample sets, thus the higher gas inflow rates of cluster centrals could be driven by the higher median stellar mass of the cluster central sample.

Table 4.2: Log of gas inflow rates ($M_{\odot}\text{Gyr}^{-1}$) at $z = 2, 3, 4$ and 6

Sample	$z = 2$	$z = 3$	$z = 4$	$z = 6$
F Satellites	10.8 ± 0.1	11.1 ± 0.2	11.0 ± 0.2	10.2 ± 0.6
F Centrals	10.9 ± 0.01	11.1 ± 0.2	11.0 ± 0.3	10.2 ± 0.6
C Satellites	10.7 ± 0.7	11.1 ± 0.3	11.2 ± 0.2	10.4 ± 0.6
C Centrals	11.4 ± 0.3	11.5 ± 0.3	11.4 ± 0.5	10.8 ± 0.6

4.4.1 Gas Inflow Rates: Before and After Infall

In Figure 4.3, we find that the cluster satellites undergo a drastic change and the gas inflow rates decrease by ≈ 0.5 dex in ~ 1.5 Gyrs ($z = 4$ to 2), but the same is not observed in field satellites. In this section, we investigate how the gas inflow rates of satellite galaxies in cluster ($M_{\text{halo}} \geq 10^{13}M_{\odot}$) and field ($M_{\text{halo}} < 10^{13}M_{\odot}$) halos change before and after infall into their host halo at $z = 2$.

We measure the infall time of satellite galaxies at $z = 2$ in the following manner. We assume that the merger tree of the most massive galaxy in a FOF halo also tracks the merger history of the FOF halo (Gupta et al., 2018). We identify the main progenitor branch history of each halo by selecting the host halo of the progenitor of the most massive galaxy at each previous snapshot between $2 \leq z \leq 6$. We calculate the infall times of each satellite galaxy as the snapshot when the galaxy becomes bound to the progenitor halo. Figure 4.4 shows the gas inflow rates of the cluster satellites (left panel) and field satellites (right panel) before and after their infall into the host halo at $z = 2$.

Before infall into the host halo at $z = 2$, cluster satellite sample have higher gas inflow rates compared to the stellar mass matched field centrals at $z \gtrsim 3$. At $z \lesssim 3$, the gas inflow rates of cluster satellites sample closely follows that of the field centrals. However, Gas inflow rates of field satellites closely follow that of the field centrals throughout their

Figure 4.3: Gas inflow rate histories of massive galaxies selected at $z = 2$ depend on their position in the halo. The solid lines show the bootstrapped median of gas inflow histories and the shaded region shows the 1σ error. The gas inflow rates of satellite galaxies in cluster halos (red) are higher at $z > 4$ compared to the field centrals (blue). The rate of gas inflow of total gas decreases rapidly in the satellite galaxies associated with larger cluster halos at $z < \sim 3$. The number of galaxies in each bin is given in parenthesis in each label.

history between $6 > z > 2$ (yellow solid line; Figure 4.4 right panel).

After infall into the host halo at $z = 2$, cluster satellites (red dashed line; Figure 4.4 left panel) have rapidly declining gas inflow rates. The gas inflow rates of galaxies decline by $\approx 0.6 - 0.4$ dex in ~ 1.5 Gyrs once they become bound to the massive cluster halo. In contrast, after infall into their respective host halo at $z = 2$, field satellites continue to have comparable gas inflow rates with the field centrals (yellow dashed line; Figure 4.4

Figure 4.4: The gas inflow rates in cluster satellites rapidly decline after infall, in contrast, the stellar mass matched field satellites have comparable history of gas inflow rates with the field centrals before and after infall. The red (left) and yellow (right) lines show the history of gas inflow rates of cluster (left) and field (right) satellites before (solid) and after (dashed) infall into the host halo at $z = 2$ respectively. The solid blue lines in both panels show the history of gas inflow rates for field centrals. Shaded regions show 1σ of the distribution.

right panel). The lack of decline in gas inflow rates in the field satellites suggests that the environment affects the gas inflow rate of galaxies only in massive cluster halos (median $\log M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\odot} = 13.3 \pm 0.03$).

4.4.2 Gas Inflow Rates vs Stellar Mass of a Galaxy

In Figure 4.3 we show that at $z = 2$, the massive cluster centrals (median $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 11.2 \pm 0.2$) have higher (by ~ 0.5 dex) gas inflow rates compared to the field centrals and the satellite sample (median $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 10.6 \pm 0.1$). The inflow of pristine gas provides the fuel for star formation, thus we would expect the stellar mass of the galaxy to be correlated with the net inflow of gas. We test if the high gas inflow rate of galaxies are driven by their stellar mass by investigating if the gas inflow rates of a galaxy depends on their stellar mass at different redshifts and environments.

4.4.2 Gas Inflow Rates vs Stellar Mass of a Galaxy

Figure 4.5: Before infall, the gas inflow rates of stellar mass matched field (yellow contours; top row) and cluster satellite galaxies (red contours; bottom row) are comparable at $z = 6, 4$ and 2.6 (left to right). The blue contours in both top and bottom rows show the comparison with the field centrals at the respective redshifts. Spearman correlation coefficient (r) between gas inflow rate and stellar mass of the galaxy is presented in the respective color in each panel. The crosshairs help visually compare the gas inflow rates for the different populations at each redshift snapshot. The positive correlation of gas inflow rates with the stellar mass of field and cluster satellites at $z > 4$ vanishes at $z \leq 4$.

Figure 4.5 shows the gas inflow rates as a function of the stellar mass of the galaxy before infall for field satellites (yellow contours, top row) and cluster satellite samples (red contours, bottom row) selected at $z = 2$. The blue contours in both top and bottom rows show the comparison with gas inflow rates of the stellar mass matched field centrals selected at $z = 2$. We measure the correlation between the stellar mass of the galaxy and the gas inflow rates at $z = 6, 4$ and 2.6 by performing the Spearman correlation test for each sample set (summarised in Table 4.3).

In the early universe (at $z = 6$), the Spearman correlation coefficient (r) between the gas

Figure 4.6: After infall, the gas inflow rates of cluster satellites (red contours; bottom row) decline compared to the stellar mass matched field satellite sample (yellow contours; top row). The blue contours in both top and bottom rows show the comparison with the field centrals at the respective redshifts. Spearman correlation coefficient (r) between gas inflow rates and stellar mass of the galaxy is presented in the respective color in each panel. The crosshairs help visually compare the gas inflow rates for the different populations at each redshift snapshot. After infall into the host halo, gas inflow rates of both cluster and field satellites show no significant correlation ($r < 0.2$) with the stellar mass of the galaxy.

inflow rates and the stellar mass of the field centrals, field satellites and cluster satellites are $r \geq 0.7$ indicating a strong positive correlation (Table 4.3). The strength of correlation between gas inflow rates and stellar mass of the galaxy decreases with decreasing redshift. At $z = 4$, the correlation between gas inflow rates and stellar mass is moderate for field centrals and weak for the satellite sample (both field and cluster). By $z = 2.6$, there is no significant correlation between the gas inflow rates with the stellar mass of the field satellites, field centrals and cluster satellites ($r < 0.2$).

After infall in the host halo, field and cluster satellites show no significant correlation ($r < 0.2$; at $z = 2$ in Table 4.3) between the gas inflow rates and the stellar mass of the galaxy at $3 \geq z \geq 2$ (Figure 4.6). However, at $z = 2$ a population of cluster satellites have lower gas inflow rates compared to the field centrals and field satellites. We investigate the cause of low gas inflow in the cluster satellite population in Section 4.4.4.

4.4.3 Gas Inflow Rates vs Host Halo Mass

In Figure 4.3, we show that the cluster centrals ($M_{\text{halo}} \geq 10^{13} M_{\odot}$) have higher (≈ 0.5 dex) gas inflow rates compared to the field centrals ($M_{\text{halo}} < 10^{13} M_{\odot}$) at $z = 2$. In contrast, the satellite sample show an inverse relation at $z = 2$ such that the field satellites have higher gas inflow rates than the cluster satellites. As halos grow by accreting smaller halos, they also accrete gas which becomes available for galaxies to accrete as inflows. Thus, in this section, we explore the correlation between gas inflow rates of galaxies with their host halo mass at different redshifts.

Figure 4.8 shows the history of gas inflow rates of field centrals and cluster centrals selected at $z = 2$. The gas inflow rates are presented at $z = 6, 3$ and 2 against the host halo mass of the galaxies at respective redshifts. Again, we calculate the Spearman correlation coefficient (r) to quantify any correlation between the gas inflow rates of the galaxies and their host halo masses (Table 4.3). Gas inflow rates in cluster and field centrals show a very strong correlation with the host halo mass in the early universe till $z = 3$, after which the strength of the correlation is moderate by $z = 2$ (Table 4.3).

Throughout the history ($6 > z > 2$) of central galaxies, the cluster centrals occupy higher halo masses (median $\log M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\odot} = 13.2 \pm 0.03$ at $z = 2$) and have higher correlation between gas inflow rates and their host halo masses compared to the field centrals (median

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$\log M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\odot} = 12.3 \pm 0.02$ at $z = 2$). The high value of r indicates that the gas inflow rates of centrals are dependent on their host halo mass at $6 > z > 2$, and the strength of the correlation at each redshift increases with increasing halo mass (Table 4.3).

Figure 4.7: History of gas inflow rates of stellar mass matched field and cluster satellite galaxies (shown in yellow and red contours respectively) vs parent halo mass of the galaxy at $z = 6, 3$ and 2 (left to right). The gas inflow rates of both cluster and field satellites show a significant positive correlation with the halo mass of the host halo at $z = 6$, however by $z \leq 3$, gas inflow rates have no significant dependence on the host halo mass of the galaxy. The crosshairs help visually compare the gas inflow rates- host halo mass plane relation for the different populations at each redshift snapshot.

Figure 4.7 shows the history of gas inflow rates of stellar mass matched field satellites and cluster satellites at $z = 6, 3$ and 2 . In the early universe at $z = 6$, we find a strong positive correlation between the gas inflow rates in galaxies and their respective host halo masses in both cluster satellites and field satellites (Table 4.3). At $z = 6$, the cluster and field satellites are associated with halos of similar halo masses and have comparable gas inflow rates. By $z = 3$, the gas inflow rates in field satellites and their host halo mass show moderate correlation, in contrast, the cluster satellites show no significant correlation (Table 4.3). By $z = 2$, both field and cluster satellites show no significant correlation (Table 4.3) between the gas inflow rates and their host halo mass.

We show in Figure 4.6 and Section 4.4.1, that a population of cluster satellites have lower gas inflow rates compared to the field centrals at $z = 2$. The lack of correlation between the gas inflow rate in the cluster satellites with their host halo mass indicate that the lower gas inflow rates in this population of cluster satellites is not driven by the host halo mass. We investigate the cause of low gas inflow rate in this population in Section 4.4.4.

Figure 4.8: History of gas inflow rates of field and cluster central galaxies selected at $z = 2$ (shown in yellow and red contours respectively) vs parent halo mass of the galaxy at $z = 6, 3$ and 2 (left to right). The gas inflow rates of both cluster and field centrals show a significant positive correlation with the halo mass of the host halo at $z = 6$, however by $z \leq 3$, gas inflow rates have no significant dependence on the host halo mass of the galaxy. The crosshairs help visually compare the gas inflow rates- host halo mass plane relation for the different populations at each redshift snapshot.

4.4.4 Gas Inflow Rates vs Halo-centric Distance

We show in section 4.4.1 and Figure 4.4 that after infall, the gas inflow rates decrease rapidly in satellites of cluster halos only. However, we show that the gas inflow rates for satellite galaxies at $z = 2$ do not depend on the host halo mass. To resolve the seemingly contradictory results, we consider the correlation of gas inflow rates and the halo-centric distance.

Figure 4.9 shows gas inflow rates of the stellar mass matched field satellites and the cluster satellites as a function of their halo-centric distance at $z = 2$. We calculate the proper distance (R) of the galaxies from the halo center (defined by the position of the particle with minimum gravitational potential energy) and normalize it by R_{200} (radius of a sphere centered at the halo center where mean density is 200 times the critical density of the Universe) at $z = 2$. We calculate the Spearman correlation coefficient (r) between the gas inflow rates of satellite galaxies and their R/R_{200} and report in Table (4.3).

The gas inflow rate is weakly correlated to R/R_{200} for field satellites and moderately correlated for cluster satellites (Table 4.3). The stellar mass matched cluster satellites

Table 4.3: Correlation Coefficient between Gas inflow rates and Galaxy Properties

Sample	M_* ($z=2$)	M_* ($z=3$)	M_* ($z=6$)	M_{halo} ($z=2$)	M_{halo} ($z=3$)	M_{halo} ($z=6$)	R/R_{200} ($z=2$)	$\log D_5$ ^a ($z=2$)
F Satellites	0.10	0.36	0.10	0.11	0.46	0.78	0.36	0.0
F Centrals	0.11	0.13	0.11	0.39	0.45	0.88	-	-0.40
C Satellites	0.16	-0.17	0.16	0.01	0.19	0.92	0.54	0.27
C Centrals	-	-	-	0.55	0.72	0.95	-	-0.67

^a $\log D_5$ is inversely proportional to local overdensity, hence, a negative value of correlation coefficient (r) implies a positive correlation of gas inflow rate with the local overdensity.

occupy the halo closer to the cluster center (median $R/R_{200} = 0.5 \pm 0.2$ kpc) and have lower gas inflow rates compared to the field satellites (median $R/R_{200} = 0.9 \pm 0.1$ kpc). This indicates that after galaxies fall into the massive cluster halos, their gas inflow rates decrease as they approach the halo center (Table 4.2).

4.4.5 Gas Inflow Rates vs Local Overdensity

In this section, we investigate the effect of local overdensity on the gas inflow rates of galaxies. We calculate the local overdensity by measuring the proper distance of the fifth nearest neighbor (D_5 ; neighbor $\log(M_*/M_\odot) \geq 8$) for each galaxy at $z = 2$. Figure 4.10 shows gas inflow rates of the four sample sets as a function of the fifth nearest neighbor distance.

We calculate the Spearman correlation coefficient (r) between the gas inflow rates and the fifth nearest neighbor distance (D_5). The gas inflow rates in cluster and field centrals are positively correlated with the local overdensity at $z = 2$ (Table 4.3). The cluster centrals are in higher density environments (median $\log D_5 = 1.6 \pm 0.1$ kpc) and have higher gas inflow rates compared to field centrals (median $\log D_5 = 2.2 \pm 0.02$ kpc; Table 4.2). This indicates an effect of local overdensity on the gas inflow rates of centrals.

The cluster satellite galaxies show a weak negative correlation between gas inflow rates and the local overdensity. However, gas inflow rates in field satellites show no correlation with the local overdensity. The cluster satellite galaxies are in higher density environments (median $\log D_5 = 1.9 \pm 0.04$ kpc) and have lower gas inflow rates compared to field satellites (median $\log D_5 = 2.0 \pm 0.1$ kpc). Contrary to the effect on centrals, the local overdensity

Figure 4.9: The gas inflow rate of cluster satellites (red contours; right panel) show a positive moderate correlation with the halo-centric radii normalized by R_{200} of the host halo at $z = 2$. In contrast, the gas inflow rate of field satellites (yellow contours; left panel) shows a weak correlation with the halo-centric distance. The contours show the distribution of stellar mass matched sample of field satellite and cluster satellite galaxies on gas mass inflow rates - halo-centric radii plane respectively. The Correlation coefficient (r) for each sample is shown in respective panels.

has a negative effect on the gas inflow rates of satellite galaxies.

4.5 Discussion

Gas inflow in galaxies is expected to depend on the galaxy environment. We use `IllustrisTNG` cosmological simulations to study the effect of environment on the gas inflow rates in massive galaxies ($\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) \geq 10.5$) at $z \geq 2$. We select central and satellites galaxy samples in low mass (field; $M_{\text{halo}} < 10^{13}M_{\odot}$) and high mass (cluster; $M_{\text{halo}} \geq 10^{13}M_{\odot}$) halos at $z = 2$. Furthermore, we have stellar mass matched the field satellite and centrals with the cluster satellite sample. The same can not be done for the cluster centrals because they are ≈ 4 times more massive (median $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 11.2 \pm 0.2$) compared to the cluster satellite galaxies (median $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) = 10.6 \pm 0.1$). Our analysis supports a picture where gas inflow rates vary as a function of environment as characterized by mass of the host halo, halo-centric radius, and local overdensity.

Figure 4.10: Gas inflow rate Vs local overdensity (quantified as 5th nearest neighbor distance; D_5) for stellar mass matched cluster satellites (red contours; left top), field satellites (yellow contours; right top) and field centrals (blue contours; right bottom) at $z = 2$. The teal contours show the gas inflow rates of cluster centrals (not stellar mass matched) at $z = 2$. The correlation coefficient (r) for each sample is shown in respective panels. The gas inflow rates in cluster and field centrals show a positive correlation with the local overdensity. The cluster satellites show a weak negative correlation with the local overdensity. In contrast, field satellites show no correlation with the local overdensity.

4.5.1 Cluster vs Field

Satellite galaxies in cluster halos selected at $z = 2$ have high gas inflow rates compared to the field centrals before infall into the host halo (solid red line in Figure 4.4). After the infall into massive cluster halos, gas inflow rates in cluster satellites rapidly decline (dashed red line in Figure 4.4). However, the same trend is not observed in the field satellite galaxies selected at $z = 2$, that show comparable gas inflow rates with the field centrals before and after infall (yellow solid and dashed lines in Figure 4.4).

Similar to our result with *IllustrisTNG*, studies using other simulations like Simha et al. (2009) find that at $z = 0$, gas accretion rates in satellite galaxies have declined to zero within 0.5-1 Gyrs after infall. At $z = 2$, we find that the gas inflow rates in cluster satellites decline by ≈ 0.5 dex in 1 Gyr after their infall into massive host halos. In agreement with our results, Simha et al. (2009) and van de Voort et al. (2017b) also find a divergence in gas inflow rates of satellite sample from the stellar mass matched "control" central sample only when the satellite sample are residing in more massive halos.

In section 4.4.4, we show the dependence of gas inflow rates of cluster and field satellite galaxies on the halo centric distance. Both cluster and field satellites (stellar mass matched) have lower gas inflow rates as they approach the halo center. The trend is stronger in cluster satellites compared to the field satellites. We also find that the massive field satellites are in the outskirts (median $\log R/R_{200} = 0.9 \pm -0.1$) of the halo, in contrast the massive cluster satellites are closer (median $\log R/R_{200} = 0.5 \pm -0.2$) to the halo center (Figure. 4.9; Table 4.1). The gas inflow rates in cluster satellites is lower compared to the cluster centrals as the gas in the halo is directed towards the center of the halo's gravitational potential. The lower gas inflow rates in cluster satellite would thus result in lower total gas fraction and lead to quenching due to gas starvation as observed in Harshan et al. (2020).

4.5.2 Centrals vs Satellites

The gas inflow rates in satellite galaxies decreases with decreasing halo-centric distance (Figure 4.9). Cluster satellites within $\sim R_{200}$ radii have lower gas inflow rates and drive the decline in the median gas inflow rates of the entire cluster satellite sample at $z = 2$ (median $\log R/R_{200} = 0.5 \pm 0.2$, Figure 4.4). Similar decline in gas inflow rates is not

measured in the field satellite sample because they are in the outskirts of the halo (median $\log R/R_{200} = 0.9 \pm 0.1$; Figure 4.9).

Contrary to the satellites, gas inflow rates in central galaxies of both cluster and field halos have a strong dependence on the host halo mass throughout $z = 6 - 2$ (Figure 4.8) and with the local overdensity, such that the gas inflow rates increases with increasing local overdensity (Figure 4.10). van de Voort et al. (2017a) and Simha et al. (2009) also find comparable results.

The emerging scenario from our results is that after infall, satellite galaxies in massive cluster halos compete for gas with the cluster halo and the central galaxy (closer to the lowest point in halo potential and higher local overdensity). We confirm the effect of environment on gas inflow increases with increasing halo mass and as the galaxies approach the halo center. Thus, gas inflow rates in satellite galaxies in field halos (that tend to be in the outskirts of the halo) are not affected by the environment (Figure 4.10; Table 4.1).

4.5.3 Comparing Gas Fractions and Gas Inflow Rates from Observations to IllustrisTNG

In Harshan et al. (2021), we find that the total gas fraction is lower only in the most massive protocluster galaxies compared to the field galaxies. In this work, we show that the total gas inflow rates (primordial + mergers) in the cluster satellite galaxies is lower than the field counterparts. We also find that the cluster satellites have a higher gas inflow rates compared to their field counterparts until $z \gtrsim 3$ before their infall into the cluster potential. This indicates that in the formative stages of the clusters, satellite galaxies have higher gas inflow rates than field galaxies. This is consistent with observational studies that find a higher molecular gas fraction in galaxies in the protocluster environment (Cucciati et al., 2014; Noble et al., 2017; Rudnick et al., 2017) at $z \sim 2$.

Direct detection of gas inflow rates continues to be elusive in observations at high redshifts and relies heavily on $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission, CGM absorption studies with quasar sightlines and mass-metallicity relation. In the past few decades an increasing number of proto-cluster/filament galaxies at $z > 2$ with a higher frequency of $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission line detections have been made (Cantalupo et al., 2014; Daddi et al., 2021; Hennawi et al., 2015; Umehata et al., 2019). Although $\text{Ly}\alpha$ emission is used to identify gravitation driven gas inflows,

the interpretation of Ly α emission is not without degeneracies. Often, Ly α emission can be explained by outflows and photo-ionization by star formation and quasar. Within the limitation interpretation of Ly α studies like Christopher Martin et al. (2014); Daddi et al. (2021); Umehata et al. (2019) find that galaxies in filaments, galaxy groups or protoclusters have active cold gas inflows. In context of our results from *IllustrisTNG*, higher gas inflow rates are associated with infalling cluster satellites.

Previous observational studies also infer the effect of environment on gas accretion using the environmental effects on mass-metallicity relations and find conflicting results. At $z \sim 2$ studies like Alcorn et al. (2019); Kacprzak et al. (2015) find no significant difference between the metallicities of protocluster and field galaxies, Shimakawa et al. (2015b) find higher metallicities in protocluster and Chartab et al. (2021) find lower metallicities in galaxies in overdense environments. Shimakawa et al. (2015b) hypothesise that the enhancement of metallicity in protocluster galaxies is due to the gas stripping, in contrast Chartab et al. (2021) hypothesise that the lower metallicities in galaxies in the overdense environments are due to effective cooling and higher gas inflow. Comparing with our results from *IllustrisTNG* simulations, these observational results could be explained by different stages of protocluster assembly or selection of central and satellite galaxies. We also note that metallicity indicators using nebular emission lines trace the ionized ISM and hence may not be robust means of interpreting primordial gas inflows.

In Harshan et al. (2021) by constructing star formation histories using SED fitting of multi-wavelength data (0.1 - 1 microns), we find that the massive galaxies in the protocluster environment have formed $45 \pm 8\%$ of their total stellar mass by $z = 3$ compared to field galaxies that have formed $31 \pm 2\%$ of their total stellar mass. Using *IllustrisTNG*, we find that the difference in star formation histories could be driven by the lower total gas fraction in progenitors in the history of massive cluster galaxies compared to the field counterparts. This indicates that the selected massive protocluster galaxies had lower gas inflows (from primordial inflow + mergers) at $z < \sim 5$. In context of the results presented in this chapter, we can confirm that the lower gas fraction of proto-cluster galaxies is in part due to lower gas inflow rates in cluster satellite galaxies at $z < 4$. Thus the the observed onset of decline in star formation rates in $z = 2$ massive protoclusters galaxies is driven by gas starvation. Quenching due to gas starvation observed in clusters at $z = 2$ would give rise to the massive quenched population of cluster galaxies at $z < 0.5$.

The declining gas inflow rate of the cluster satellites after infall indicate that the gas that

would have been accreted into the cluster satellite galaxies is redirected to the cluster potential and the cluster centrals. Thus cluster centrals have an increasing (at $z = 6-3$) and then a constant (at $z = 3-2$) gas inflow rates. The gas that is accreted onto the cluster halo would eventually build the hot ICM that is observed in $z > 1$ clusters (Rabitz et al., 2017; Stanford et al., 2001) and likely further affect the gas accretion onto cluster galaxies. We will extend our work and investigate the cause of constant gas inflow rates in centrals (at $z = 4 - 2$) and the effect of the ICM on gas inflow rates in a future study.

4.6 Summary

In Harshan et al. (2021), we find that the lower star formation in massive protocluster galaxies compared to the field galaxies at $z = 2$ is driven by lower total gas fractions since $z \sim 5$. To investigate the cause of lower total gas fractions in protocluster galaxies, we study gas inflow rates. In this work, we use `IllustrisTNG` cosmological simulations to understand the role of environment in driving the gas inflow rates in the massive ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) galaxies. We divide our sample into centrals and satellites in cluster ($M_{\text{halo}} \geq 10^{13}M_\odot$) and field ($M_{\text{halo}} < 10^{13}M_\odot$) halos. Our main results are summarised as follows:

- 1) History of gas inflow rates at $6 > z > 2$: Until $z = 2$, gas inflow rates in cluster centrals is higher compared to the field centrals. At $z = 2$, gas inflow rates in cluster centrals ($\log \dot{M}_{\text{in,gas}} = 11.4 \pm 0.3 M_\odot \text{Gyr}^{-1}$) are ≈ 0.5 dex higher compared to field centrals ($\log \dot{M}_{\text{in,gas}} = 10.9 \pm 0.01 M_\odot \text{Gyr}^{-1}$). The cluster satellites also have higher gas inflow rates compared to the stellar mass matched field centrals at $6 > z > \sim 4$ (Figure. 4.3). At $z < \sim 3$, the gas inflow rates in cluster satellites rapidly declines (by $\approx 0.4-0.6$ dex) as they fall into the cluster potential. However, the history of gas inflow rates in field satellite galaxies do not show this trend and closely follow that of the field centrals (Figure. 4.4).
- 2) Gas inflow rates as a function of stellar mass: We find a correlation of gas inflow rates of cluster and field satellites and field centrals with the stellar mass of the galaxies at $z > 4$ (Figure. 4.5). However, at $z < 4$, we find no significant dependence of gas inflow rates on the stellar mass of the galaxies irrespective of their position in the halo (Figure. 4.6).
- 3) Gas inflow rates as a function of halo mass: At $z > 4$, we find a strong correlation between the gas inflow rates of both cluster and field satellites, which is not observed at

$z < 4$. By $z = 2$, the gas inflow rates of the cluster satellites decline compared to the field satellites (Figure 4.7). On the other hand, gas inflow rates of the central galaxies are strongly correlated with the host halo mass until $z = 2$ (Figure 4.8). This indicates that satellites are competing for gas accretion with the centrals that have an advantageous position in the halo.

4) Gas inflow rates as a function of halo-centric distance: Gas inflow rates of cluster satellites show a moderate correlation with the halo-centric radius such that the inflow rates decrease as galaxies approach the cluster center. A weak correlation between gas inflow rate and halo-centric distance is seen in the field satellites. Massive field satellites are also on average in the outskirts of the field halo, unlike the cluster satellites.

5) Gas inflow rates as a function of local overdensity: Gas inflow rates of central galaxies in both field and cluster halos are positively correlated with the local overdensity. Cluster centrals that live in higher mass halos and higher local overdensity have significantly higher gas inflow rates compared to the field centrals. Our results indicate that gas inflow rates for centrals are primarily governed by the host halo mass and the local overdensity at $z = 2$. However, the gas inflow rates in cluster satellites only show a weak negative correlation with the local overdensity and the field satellites show no correlation with the local overdensity. This indicates that for satellite galaxies halo mass and hence local overdensity does not affect the gas inflow rates.

We show that the effect of environment on the evolution of galaxies becomes significant in the very early universe (at $z \sim 3-4$). Unlike the effects of environment in the local universe which are driven by galaxy-galaxy interactions or hydrodynamical interactions with the intracluster medium, in the early universe, the effect of environment on galaxies is driven by gas accretion that is correlated with the galaxies' position in the cosmic web (e.g., central vs satellite and high vs low host halo mass). While the gas inflow rates in centrals are correlated mainly by the host halo mass and the local overdensity, gas inflow rates for satellite galaxies is correlated with the halo-centric distance and the time since infall.

The rapid decline in gas inflow in cluster satellites and the high gas inflow in cluster centrals indicate that the gas is redirected from the satellites to the cluster halo. This redirected gas should build up (starting as early as $z \sim 3$) to form the ICM and is also accreted onto the cluster centrals. In contrast the cluster satellites with declining gas

inflow rates become gas starved eventually decreasing their star formation rates. Thus the quenching of the massive cluster satellites driven by starvation as shown in this work would lead to the build up of the massive quenched cluster populations that is observed in the local universe. We plan for a future study to understand the build-up of ICM, halo mass and its effect on the gas inflow rates of the centrals and satellites.

Further investigation of the inflowing gas by distinguishing the multi-phase gas and studying the evolution to $z = 0$ is required to understand the build up of ICM and quenching in cluster galaxies driven by gas starvation. While the observational signature for gas accretion remains elusive, with future multi-wavelength observational campaigns producing deep spatially resolved spectroscopy and mass-metallicity measurements of high redshift galaxies will be able to understand the evolution of gas inflow rates and test the predictions made in cosmological simulations.

Chapter 5

Summary and Future Work

5.1 General Summary

In the local universe, the effect of environment is well studied and is known to be driven by galaxy-galaxy interactions or the interactions with the intra-cluster medium (Cortese et al., 2021; Morokuma-Matsui et al., 2021; Vulcani et al., 2018). These environmental processes affect the average star formation, metallicity, stellar mass function, etc. in the cluster/ high density environments. However, when and how the environmental processes start affecting the evolution of galaxies has yet to be fully understood.

In this thesis, we attempt to understand the role of environment in the early universe. We study protocluster galaxies at $z \sim 2$ from the ZFIRE (Nanayakkara et al., 2016; Tran et al., 2015) and ZFOURGE (Straatman et al., 2016) surveys and compare our results with IllustrisTNG cosmological simulations (Nelson et al., 2018; Pillepich et al., 2018a). We measure the average electron density and star formation histories of galaxies in protocluster and field environment, and find that the properties of galaxies in protocluster environments have started to diverge from the galaxies in low density environments at $z \sim 2$. We find that the star formation histories in IllustrisTNG are comparable to our observational results. Furthermore, by tracking the evolution of galaxies in IllustrisTNG, we find that the star formation suppression observed in massive protocluster galaxies is driven by gas starvation. Our results from IllustrisTNG indicate that the low total gas fraction and gas inflow in protocluster galaxies is driven by their position in the cosmic web and thus

their access to the primordial gas.

Our work studying the history of star formation and gas inflows using observations and simulations are a first step towards understanding the history of the evolution of cluster galaxies as opposed to studying the difference in properties in different environment populations at certain time snapshots. Although studying the history of galaxy properties in observations is complex, it is becoming increasingly more accessible using SED fitting routines being able to reconstruct star formation and metallicity histories (Johnson et al., 2021; Leja et al., 2017; Robotham et al., 2020). We also show that rather than the evolution of galaxies in over-dense environments "diverging" compared to the galaxies in the field environment, the position of the galaxies in the cosmic web when they are formed determines their fate.

5.2 Electron Density at $z = 1.62$ as a Function of Environment

In the local universe, cluster galaxies have low star formation activity (Lewis et al., 2002a; Peng et al., 2010) and lower molecular gas fractions (Boselli et al., 2014; Fumagalli et al., 2009). Contrary to the findings in the local universe, the UDS protocluster at $z = 1.62$ has a higher star formation density (Tran et al., 2010) and a significant molecular gas fraction (Noble et al., 2017; Rudnick et al., 2017). These results indicate that the UDS protocluster is in the nascent stages of its assembly, hence we test whether the ISM properties of the protocluster galaxies are starting to diverge from their field counterparts.

We measure the average electron density of 6 protocluster galaxies at $z = 1.62$ using [OII] ($\lambda 3726, \lambda 3729$) doublet ratio and compare our measurements with existing literature measurements at $z \sim 1.5$. We find that the protocluster galaxies have three times higher (with $\sim 2.6\sigma$ confidence) electron density ($n_e = 366 \pm 84 \text{cm}^{-3}$) compared to the field sample ($n_e = 104 \pm 55 \text{cm}^{-3}$) (Harshan et al., 2020). The low numbers in the sample along with high scatter in our measurements make the result tentative only. In contrast to our results, Darvish et al. (2015) find ≈ 17 times lower electron density for galaxies in the high density filamentary structures at $z = 0.5$. This difference could be explained by the evolution of ISM properties and electron density in different environments across cosmic time or be indicative of environmental impact on the ISM occurring at a later stage in the

cluster assembly, e.g. at $z < 1$ as observed by Darvish et al. (2015).

We compare our measurement at $z = 1.62$ to the SDSS sample and find that the electron density of galaxies in the stellar mass, SFR and sSFR matched sample decreases by a factor of ~ 8.5 from $z = 1.62$ ($n_e = 254 \pm 76 \text{cm}^{-3}$) to $z = 0$ ($n_e = 30 \pm 1 \text{cm}^{-3}$). However, we do not find a significant correlation between electron density and stellar mass, SFR or sSFR. Further deep observational campaigns targeting galaxies in protoclusters of varying halo masses at $z \geq 1.5$ are required to conclusively prove the effect of environment on the electron density of galaxies.

5.3 Signs of Star Formation Suppression in Massive Proto-cluster Galaxies at $z = 2$

Thomas et al. (2010) find that the early-type galaxies in clusters in the local universe would have formed ≈ 2 Gyrs earlier than their field counterparts. In this work, by reconstructing the star formation histories (SFH) of galaxies in a protocluster environment at $z = 2$, we test whether the protocluster galaxies have formed and evolved earlier than the field galaxies. We use ZFIRE-ZFOURGE observational data with Prospector SED fitting code (Johnson et al., 2021; Leja et al., 2019) to measure the SFHs.

We find that the massive galaxies ($\log M_*/M_\odot \geq 10.5$) have a flat/ declining SFH compared to the lower mass ($9 \geq \log M_*/M_\odot \geq 9.5$) galaxies that have a rising SFH (Harshan et al., 2021). Comparable to other studies (Darvish et al., 2017; Donnari et al., 2021; Kawinwanichakij et al., 2017a; Muzzin et al., 2012; Tomczak et al., 2016; Webb et al., 2020), we find that the high mass galaxies irrespective of their environment at $z = 2$ formed the majority of stars earlier compared to the lower mass galaxies. We also do not find a significant effect of environment on the SFH of lower mass galaxies ($9 \geq \log M_*/M_\odot \geq 10.5$). However, we find that the massive protocluster galaxies are showing signs of star formation suppression compared to the field galaxies in the same stellar mass bin. The massive protocluster galaxies have formed $45 \pm 8\%$ of their stars in the first 2 Gyrs since the Big Bang compared to the field galaxies that have formed $31 \pm 2\%$ of their stellar mass indicating an effect of environment and the beginning of star formation quenching. We find qualitatively similar SFHs in IllustrisTNG cosmological simulations compared to our observational results.

We use IllustrisTNG to probe the physical mechanisms driving the SFHs in different environments. We measure the mass weighted stellar ages of the galaxies in different environments and find that the lower mass galaxies are ≈ 190 Myrs younger than the high mass galaxies. However, there is no significant difference in stellar ages with environment in all stellar mass bins, ruling out the scenario of early formation and evolution of protocluster galaxies leading to the suppression of star formation in massive protocluster galaxies. We also check the merger histories and the cold gas fraction in major and minor mergers till $z = 2$ and find no significant effect of environment. By measuring the total gas fractions in all of the progenitors of galaxies in different environments, we find that the massive protocluster galaxies have had lower total gas fractions in the stellar disks of their progenitors since ~ 1 Gyr after the Big Bang compared to the field galaxies. We hypothesize that the lower star formation in massive protocluster galaxies is a delayed cumulative effect of having low gas fractions.

5.4 Lower Gas Inflow Rates in Satellite Galaxies in Massive Halos

In chapter 3, we identify lower total gas fraction in the progenitors of massive protocluster galaxies as a cause of star formation suppression. Hence, we investigate the role of gas inflow in driving the lower gas fractions in the progenitors of massive protocluster galaxies. We divide massive galaxies ($\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 10.5$) into centrals and satellites associated to cluster ($M_{\text{halo}} \geq 10^{13}M_\odot$) and field ($M_{\text{halo}} < 10^{13}M_\odot$) halos. We measure the history of gas inflow rates of the four sample sets and investigate the effect of environment by studying their correlation with the stellar mass, halo mass, halo-centric radii and the local overdensity.

We find that the gas inflow rates in centrals are mainly driven by the halo mass of the galaxies since $z = 6$ to $z = 2$. At $z = 2$, central galaxies also show a significant positive correlation with the local overdensity. Whereas, satellites galaxies show no significant dependence on the host halo mass after infall at $z = 2$. Gas inflow rates of satellite galaxies show moderate dependence on the halo centric distance such that the gas inflow rates decreases as galaxies approach the cluster center. We also see a weak negative correlation of gas inflow rates in cluster satellite galaxies with the local overdensity and no correlation between gas inflow rates of the field satellites and their local overdensity.

The gas inflow rates of both cluster and field centrals increase and become constant at $z < 3$ depending on their host halo mass. The gas inflow rate of satellites decrease after they fall into the massive host halo (cluster). Thus, the massive cluster satellites with declining gas inflow rates at $z = 2$ would become gas starved and evolve into the massive quenched cluster galaxies observed at $z \sim 0.5$.

Our results show that in massive halos, the satellite galaxies compete for gas inflows with the cluster potential and the cluster centrals which are closer to the deepest point in the halo's gravitational potential well and hence have a comparative advantage of gas flowing towards them. We hypothesize that the gas that is diverted from the cluster satellites would contribute to the formation of the hot ICM that is observed at $z = 1$ and to the higher gas inflow rates in the cluster centrals.

5.5 Future Work

The recent launch of the James Webb Space Telescope heralds an exciting new era for extra-galactic astronomy. With JWST, the global astronomy community awaits the deepest view of the early universe ever to be produced. The planned and future ultra deep surveys will not only be able to show us the images of the first galaxies that reionised the universe, we will also be able to see the emergence of the large scale structure of the universe. Our results show that the emergence and growth of galaxies are closely related to the environment of the galaxies since very early in the Universe. Hence, prospective deep surveys with JWST combined with the state-of-the-art instruments being commissioned on the 8-10 m class telescopes, make the findings of this thesis most timely.

Our results identify three central themes (stated below) where further observations and study are required to understand how galaxies evolve in different environments.

5.5.1 Elucidating the Role of Local Galaxy Density in Galaxy Growth

Galaxies residing in low density environments are thought to have driven the reionisation of the Universe (Hutter et al., 2021). However, in chapter 3, we show that between $z=6$ to 2, galaxies in low density environments are unable to produce stars rapidly compared to the galaxies in high density environments. Thus the effect of environment on galaxy

growth needs to be further investigated in a larger data set spanning different stages of cluster formation. Although an increasing number of protoclusters are being identified at $z \sim 6$ (Calvi et al., 2019; Harikane et al., 2019; Hu et al., 2021; Ouchi et al., 2005), many are identified with photometry only. With deep spectroscopic campaigns, the large scale structure can be mapped to spectroscopically confirm the protoclusters up to $z > 6$.

Characterising the large scale structure or local overdensities would allow us to understand how the stellar mass functions evolved in different environments. By quantifying the stellar mass function in low and high density environments (Papovich et al., 2018; Tomczak et al., 2014) at $z \geq 6$, we will be able to inform the current galaxy evolution models and cosmological simulations that are currently unable to reproduce the observed populations of galaxies in the early universe accurately. By reconstructing the star formation histories using SED fitting codes like BEAGLES (Chevallard & Charlot, 2016)/PROSPECTOR (Leja et al., 2019)/ PROSPECT (Robotham et al., 2020) of galaxies in different local overdensities we would be able to study the emergence of first galaxies and confirm if the environment of the galaxy affected galaxy growth and thus reionisation of the universe.

5.5.2 Constraining Gas Inflows and Outflows in the Early Universe

Understanding the baryonic cycle is quintessential to understanding how galaxies evolve. How gas is fed into the galaxies and ejected out through feedback from the active galactic nuclei (AGN) and star formation bursts driven winds and outflows is not well constrained. In chapter 4, we show that the environment of a galaxy affect gas inflows as early as $z = 4$. Targeting cluster and field galaxies identified in the early universe with Integral Field Spectrographs (IFS) and constructing the velocity maps of galaxies in different environments will allow us to constrain inflows and outflows and confirm/refute the predictions made in chapter 4.

New multi object spectrographs and IFS instruments like MOONS (Cirasuolo et al., 2011) and ERIS (Marchetti et al., 2012) on the VLT and KAPA (Wizinowich et al., 2020) with LIGER (Wiley et al., 2020) on Keck Observatory make the study of gas kinematics for galaxies at $z > 2 - 3$ feasible. By targeting the overdensities found in the deep space based surveys e.g., from JWST, with ground based multi-object spectrographs that provide higher spatial resolution, we would be able to characterise the presence of AGN using emission line diagnostics redshifts $z \sim 3 - 6$. By taking advantage of both ground and space

based telescopes, we will be able to probe the higher kinematics in emission line spectrum of galaxies to probe the inflowing and outflowing gas. By quantifying the prevalence and strength of AGN and outflows in different density environments and comparing the results with cosmological simulations, will constrain theoretical feedback mechanisms used in large hydro-dynamical cosmological simulations.

One of the main reasons that the role of AGN feedback on galaxy evolution is not well constrained is due to the existence of outflow signatures from AGN feedback and starburst in both star forming and quenched galaxies. This highlights the need of studying AGNs in the context of their star formation histories. Identifying the origin of outflows using spectral decomposition of resolved emission line maps across star forming, starburst, post starburst and quenched galaxies and creating resolved star formation histories maps of different populations of galaxies will allow us to explore the temporal correlations between star formation and outflows.

5.5.3 Probing the Properties of the Multi-Phase Gas

In chapter 3, we find that massive galaxies in the protocluster environment are showing signs of star formation suppression at $z = 2$. Using IllustrisTNG, we predict that the suppressed star formation is due to lower gas fraction in the galaxies as early as $z \sim 4.5$. Although direct observations probing molecular gas fraction for individual galaxies can only provide upper limits at $z > 3$ (Whitaker et al., 2021), gravitational lenses can be used as "cosmic telescopes" to probe the gas content in galaxies in the early universe. Combining the spectral and spatial resolution of JWST with the magnifying power of gravitational lensing, provides us excellent opportunities to study the high redshift galaxies with tremendous details. Using ALMA, we can measure the molecular Hydrogen fraction traced by the carbon monoxide (CO) spectroscopic observations for these lensed $z > 2.5$ galaxies. By combining 1.3 mm observations from ALMA with the NIR spectrum with space based photometry, we can test the predictions from IllustrisTNG presented in chapter 3 and 4 and probe the relationship between the ionised gas, molecular gas fraction, star formation histories (using SED fitting) and ISM conditions of galaxies (using emission line ratios) at $z > 2 - 3$.

Appendix A

Effect of Blackhole Feedback on Star Formation History

We explore the role of active galactic nuclei (AGN) feedback on star formation suppression in *IllustrisTNG* until $z = 2$. In chapter 3, we find that the massive protocluster galaxies at $z = 2$ are showing signs of star formation suppression. One of the pathways that lead to star formation quenching in massive galaxies is the feedback from the supermassive blackhole (SMBH)(Croton et al., 2007; Gupta et al., 2021; Zinger et al., 2020). Here we show the SMBH activity of galaxies in massive protocluster and field galaxies at $z = 2$. Following the sample selection from chapter 3, we have selected cluster galaxies as galaxies associated with halos of $\log M_{halo} \geq 13$ and field galaxies as galaxies associated with halos $\log M_{halo} < 13$. We also put an SFR cut-off of $0.39 M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$ to match the observational limitation.

For the massive galaxy sample ($\log M_{*}/M_{\odot} \geq 10.5$), figure A.1 shows the normalized distribution of the ratio of cumulative kinetic to thermal energy injection ($E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}}$) for cluster (brown) and field (teal) galaxies at $z = 2$. Massive cluster galaxies have higher median $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}} = 0.11 \pm 0.024$ compared to the field galaxies with median $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}} = 0.0016 \pm 0.0035$. Figure A.2 shows the history of blackhole mass growth (left panel) and black hole accretion rates (right panel) of cluster (brown) and field (teal) galaxies until $z = 2$. The black hole mass of the cluster galaxies is higher compared to field galaxies at 1 Gyr after the big bang. Cluster galaxies also have high blackhole accretion rates compared to the field sample until 2 Gyrs after the big bang, after which

the blackhole accretion rates decrease until 3.3 Gyrs after the big bang.

Figure A.1: Distribution of the ratio of cumulative kinetic to thermal energy injection ($E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}}$) by SMBH $z = 2$ from *IllustrisTNG*. The brown and teal histograms show the distribution of $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}}$ for cluster and field samples respectively. The dashed vertical brown and teal line shows the median $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}}$ for cluster and field galaxies and the shaded regions show 1σ error in the median. The solid black vertical line shows the transitional $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}}$ after which galaxies begin to quench. Cluster galaxies have higher $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}}$ compared to field galaxies. Median $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}}$ for both cluster and field galaxies is lower than the transitional $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}}$ of $1/3$ (solid black line).

In *IllustrisTNG*, Zinger et al. (2020) find that the AGN feedback leads to star formation quenching in galaxies when the SMBH reaches the transitional mass of $\log M_{\text{bh}}/M_{\odot} \sim 8.3$. At this mass, the kinetic energy injection becomes comparable to the thermal energy injection by the SMBH and results in a higher gas entropy in galaxies, leading to star formation quenching.

In chapter 3, we observe star formation suppression in cluster galaxies compared to field galaxies at time > 2 Gyrs since the big bang. Both field and cluster galaxies have median SMBH masses $\log M_{\text{bh}}/M_{\odot} < 8.3$ (showed as horizontal line in figure A.2, left panel)

APPENDIX A. EFFECT OF BLACKHOLE FEEDBACK ON STAR FORMATION HISTORY

at time = 2 Gyrs after the big bang. The median $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}}$ of both cluster and field galaxies $< 1/3$ at $z = 2$. At the time of onset of star formation suppression in cluster galaxies (time ~ 2 Gyrs), SMBH masses $\log M_{\text{bh}}/M_{\odot} < 8.3$ and median $E_{\text{inj,KM/QM}} < 1/3$ for both cluster and field galaxies. Thus, we conclude that the star formation suppression in cluster galaxies in this sample is not driven by the SMBH feedback

Figure A.2: History of blackhole mass growth (left panel) and blackhole accretion rates (right panel) until $z = 2$ from *IllustrisTNG*. The solid lines indicate the median blackhole mass growth and blackhole mass accretion rates for massive cluster (brown) and field (teal) galaxies. The shaded regions show 1σ error in the median. The solid black horizontal line in the left panel shows the transitional blackhole mass of $\log M_{\text{bh}}/M_{\odot} \sim 8.3$, after which galaxies begin to quench due to feedback. Although massive protocluster galaxies have higher blackhole masses compared to the field galaxies, they only reach the transitional blackhole mass after the galaxies have started to show star formation suppression.

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